

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D2.4 VITAL-5G Experimentation Platform, Open Repository, Application & Verification Tools

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AGV	Autonomous Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
DNS	Domain Name System
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
ExpB	Experiment Blueprint
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
JWT	JSON Web Token
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identifier
IP	Internet Protocol
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	Lifecycle Management
LLCM	Logistics LCM
ML	Machine Learning
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NFVO	Network functions virtualization Orchestrator
OPTICS	Ordering Points To Identify the Clustering Structure
PoAB	Port of Antwerp Bruges
TCB	TestCase Blueprint
QoE	Quality of Experience
RBAC	Role Based Access Control
REST	Representational State Transfer
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SVM	Support Vector Machine

Abbreviation / Term	Description
T&L	Transport & Logistics
TCB	TestCase Blueprint
VS	Vertical Service
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable, Low-Latency Communications
VSB	Vertical Service Blueprint
VSD	Vertical Service Descriptor
VNF	Virtual Network Function
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.4 “VITAL-5G experimentation platform, Open Repository, Application & Verification Tools” is the last deliverable of Work Package 2 “VITAL-5G Platform Implementation” of the VITAL-5G project. The latter is responsible for all the implementation work taking place within the project with respect to both the VITAL-5G experimentation Platform and the Network Applications developed by the consortium partners.

In this aspect, the scope of D2.4 is to present the final version of the VITAL-5G experimentation facility including all the updates in versions of all functionalities presented in previous deliverables and report on the specifications, architecture and experimenter guidelines. Thus, in the following sections authors present:

- An overview of the Network Applications, Services and Experiment data models, necessary for experimentation;
- A VITAL-5G platform User Guide, for 3rd party experimenters;
- The platform’s software components and assets (e.g., links to repositories, deployment information);
- A detailed description of all the Network Applications developed within VITAL-5G and representative cases of 3rd party experimenters’ Network Applications.

Indeed, following an introductory section (in Section 1), the key concepts of Network Applications and the related Network Application Packages and T&L Services information models are presented (Section 2). Indeed, in these information models different blocks of information, including component description, endpoints, 5G network requirements, hardware dependencies, software details to facilitate integrations (e.g. API specifications), deployment aspects, as well as testing and validation details.

In Section 3, authors deliver a QuickStart guide of the VITAL-5G platform for 3rd party experimenters. In more detail, potential platform users are guided through the Portal Web Graphical User Interface (GUI), where the processes for the (a) Network Application onboarding, (b) Vertical Service management, (c) Experiment execution and reporting are presented.

With respect to the VITAL-5G platform components, 14 software components are presented in detail along with links to repositories, licensing information and guidelines for installation where necessary. These cater to platform needs including Graphical User Interface, service and lifecycle management, access control, platform repository/inventories, verification tools, monitoring components, slice management and Artificial Intelligence/ Machine Learning-based components/tools for functions related to both the platform services as well as the experiments (i.e., for diagnostics, analytics and post-processing analysis). Some of these components have been presented in previous releases with major, minor or no updates for this last release of the Platform, while there are cases of completely new components targeted for this last release, such as the *Intent-based Request Manager*, an alternative mechanism to define VITAL-5G experiments by adopting an abstraction for defining them based on the natural language, and the *ML/Analytics Toolkit*, a functionality originally planned as a Network Application but was decided to be integrated in the platform, allowing users to train their own machine learning models and explore results. Particular focus is set on the closed-control loop services introduced in the platform for this final release, enabling automated mechanisms to act upon detection of computing or network infrastructure underperformances.

Concerning the Network Applications, 15 vertical-agnostic and vertical-specific applications in total have been delivered in this final release catering to the VITAL-5G Transport and Logistic use cases, but also across use cases. These Network Applications involve functionalities like sensor data ingestion & fusion, IoT management, data collection, robot navigation, human-robot collaboration, assisted vessel navigation, predictive maintenance, monitoring and others. In Section 5, all the relevant information on 3rd party access, licensing, APIs and available software assets are described in detail.

All the aforementioned components and Network Applications are delivered and functional. Their integration details will be provided in Deliverable 3.3 of the project, while they have been and will be further tested in the context of Work Package 4.

It is worth to highlight besides the successful trials of the VITAL-5G Platform and Network Applications, 9 platform components and 3 Network Applications have been released with an open-source license. In other cases, other type of access such as access to IoT, camera feed and simulation data, access to their outputs such as machine learning model results are offered. In this sense, a wide range of capabilities can be exploited in the future by any other interested party.

Lastly, the relevant repository information for Network Application Blueprints and an example to use as reference is included in Annex I, while a high-level description of representative Network Applications by 3rd party experimenters in the context of VITAL-5G is provided.

1 Introduction

1.1 Deliverable Scope

This deliverable's purpose is to provide the final implementation details regarding the VITAL-5G experimentation platform, and the Network Applications developed by the consortium in the context of Work Package (WP) 2. It should be noted that while a high-level architecture was presented first in D1.2 [1] and finalized in D1.3 [2], all the implementation aspects are part of WP2. In this aspect, previous intermediate and/or final releases and software design choices have been included in D2.1 [3], D2.2 [4] and D2.3 [5] deliverables.

As D2.4 is the last deliverable of WP2, it includes the final release of the remaining components and Network Applications, but it also aims to summarize the work done across this work package and provide a complete overview of all components and application-related final implementation information regardless of their release date.

Furthermore, it provides a detailed platform guide to assist all users and more specifically 3rd parties in onboarding, vertical service management and experimentation and an overview of the Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprints, the Experiment Descriptors and Test Case Blueprints.

1.2 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed. Table 1 summarizes the relevant tasks' and deliverable descriptions found in the GA and provides the relevant chapters and descriptions of work included in the deliverable.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Deliverable 2.4 Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 2.1 Network Applications development	The main goal of this task is the development of the vertical specific and agnostic Network Applications, that will be used in the VITAL-5G use cases and the respective relevant features...	Section 5	The deliverable includes the final description of all the Network Applications implemented within VITAL-5G related to the use cases described in Deliverable 1.1 [6].
	The first phase of this task refers to the design and implementation of Network Applications in terms of number of VNFs in a service chain, and placement of VNFs on top of the vertical and cross-vertical infrastructure...	Section 5, Section 2, Annex I	Section covers all the design and implementation aspects of the Network Applications in question as they have evolved, while in Annex I the relevant indicative blueprints can be found. Section 2 offers a detailed description on the definition of Network Applications and the related data models for Network Application Packages and T&L Services.

	<p>The developed Network Applications will be available ... to be used by 3rd party experimenters, while the necessary functionality and tools will be developed to allow for the creation, onboarding and instantiation of additional Network Applications by other experimenters.</p>	<p>Section 5, Section 2, Section 3</p>	<p>Section 5 provides all the related Network Application information and provides the repository information for 3rd party experimenters, while Section 4 describes the final version of the VITAL-5G Platform that includes the necessary functionality and tools for creation, onboarding and instantiation. Sections 2 & 3 offer (a) a description on the data models for Network Applications, Services and Experiments, (b) a comprehensive VITAL-5G Platform guide for the Network Application onboarding, vertical service managements and experiment execution respectively.</p>
<p>Task 2.2 VITAL-5G platform enhancement & Open repository development</p>	<p>This task deals with the implementation of the VITAL-5G's Open platform two main blocks: VITAL-5G Portal and the Open Online repository.</p>	<p>Section 4</p>	<p>Section 4 describes the final version of the VITAL-5G Platform, incl. the Portal and Open Online Repository. It focuses on the evolution of these blocks compared to the details provided in the previous deliverable, as well as compared to the software baseline, i.e., components and software used from previous projects.</p>
<p>Task 2.3 Network Application verification tools</p>	<p>This task deals with verification and validation (V&V) tools, methodologies and benchmarking procedures....</p> <p>The V&V tools will be developed (potentially building on existing tools) and will be used ...to pre-validate the Network Applications and -in the field- by using the VITAL-5G platform for full validation of Network Applications.</p>	<p>Section 4</p>	<p>Section 4 provides a comprehensive description of the VITAL-5G Platform and as such the relevant V&V tools. It focuses on the evolution of these blocks compared to the details provided in the previous deliverable, as well as compared to the software baseline, i.e., components and software used from previous projects.</p>
<p>Task 2.4 Application & intelligence development</p>	<p>This task will be responsible for the implementation of innovative applications which based on the enhanced capabilities of</p>	<p>Section 4, Section 5</p>	<p>The document describes a wide range of functionalities whether related to the VITAL-5G Platform (Section 4) or to the Network Application capabilities (Section 5), based on Machine Learning and Artificial intelligence techniques.</p>

	<p>5G connectivity will deliver added-value intelligence to the T&L tasks required by the VITAL-5G use cases. AI and ML techniques will be utilized to offer significantly improved automation, self-management and self-configuration capabilities to the developed logistics functionalities, while advanced post-processing, Big Data, distributed data ingestion/fusion techniques will allow for continuous (self) optimization of the applications.</p>		<p>Such capabilities include automation, self-management and self-configuration, advanced post-processing employing ML/AI approaches, distributed data ingestion and fusion techniques.</p>
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D2.4 VITAL-5G experimentation platform, Open Repository, Application & verification tools [R/O, PU, M30] The final version of the VITAL-5G experimentation facility including updated versions of all functions and a final report on the specifications, architecture and experimenter guidelines.</p>			

1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

As deliverable 2.4 is the last deliverable of WP2, it aims to present the work carried out within the WP, but also the additions and changes that have been made compared to previous WP2 deliverables. More specifically:

- The current section introduces the scope and structure of the deliverable.
- Section 2 presents an overview of the definition of a Network Application and the relevant data models for the network application packages and T&L Services.
- Section 3 presents the VITAL-5G platform, describing in detail processes like Network Application onboarding, Vertical Service management and experiment-related aspects.
- Section 4 includes a detailed overview of the VITAL-5G platform new and existing (from previous releases) components.
- Section 5 offers a detailed description of the final version of all the VITAL-5G Network Applications.
- Lastly, Section 6 includes the closing remarks of the deliverable.

2 Network Applications, Services and Experiment data models

2.1 Network Application Definition and Characterization

The key concept behind VITAL-5G is the concept of Network Application, which aims on the one side to enable mechanisms to simplify the vertical application definition and composition, and on the other side ease the management and allocation of the 5G network slices required by the application or services. In this sense, a VITAL-5G Network Application extends the typical orchestration related descriptors, enabling enhanced mechanisms for:

- i. 5G slice profile endpoint specification;
- ii. Definition of the metrics to be collected automatically by the VITAL-5G Platform centralized monitoring;
- iii. Enabling enhanced mechanisms for service-oriented API specification for eased service composition.

In detail, in Figure 1 we represent the different blocks of information contained in a Network Application Package, as originally established in D1.3 [2].

Figure 1: High-level representation of a Network Application package.

2.2 Information Models of Network Application Packages and T&L Services

In deliverable D2.1 [3] we presented the initial model aiming at delivering metadata information necessary for the Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprints (VSBs), and in D2.3 [5] we extended them with the establishment of information models of the Experiment Descriptors and TestCase Blueprints (TCBs). In this deliverable we provide the full specification of all the VITAL-5G catalogue elements, depicted in Figure 2, in order to provide a reference document for internal and 3rd party experimenters to use during the service and experiment design phase. Moreover, the objective is to detail the enhancements performed as a consequence of the introduction of new features and due to the outcomes of the internal experimentation. In Annex I we provide concrete examples of all these blueprints and descriptors to use as reference for the definition of new Network Applications, services and experiments.

The information model and data elements related to the Network Application Blueprint are depicted in Figure 2. In this case the extensions and updates performed on this information element are:

- i. Addition of the *computeNodeCriteria* parameter, to allow service designers to establish hardware characteristics to use when selecting the compute node to deploy the application component (see D1.3 [2] section 4.2.2 for further details);

- ii. Alignment of the infrastructure metrics to match the ones supported by the *Monitoring Platform* (and the ones exposed by the testbed agents): *DISK_USAGE*, *LATENCY*, *E2E_LATENCY*, *GPU_LOAD*, *PACKET_DELIVERY_RATIO*, *PACKET_LOSS*, *JITTER*, *DROPPED_PACKETS_PER_SECOND*, *FORWARDED_PACKETS_PER_SECOND*, *DROPPED_BYTES_PER_SECOND*, *FORWARDED_BYTES_PER_SECOND*, *CPU_LOAD*, *RAM_USAGE*, *USER_EXPERIENCED_DOWNLINK_DATA_RATE*, *USER_EXPERIENCED_UPLINK_DATA_RATE*;
- iii. Addition of a field, *vnfReference* to allow to establish the specific VNF for which the platform should collect the compute related metrics (e.g., *CPU_LOAD*, etc.).

We refer to D2.1 [3] for the description of the specific fields.

Figure 2: Network Application information model.

Further details of the information model of the Slice Profile and the customization of these profiles into EMBB and URLLC slice profiles and their associated profile parameters were originally described in D2.1 [3]. It is worth

highlighting, that URLLC slice profile parameters were updated in order to be able to differentiate between upload and downlink data rates (as highlighted in Figure 3).

Figure 3: Slice Profiles and Slice Profile Parameters.

This release of the VITAL-5G platform also includes support for the license validation, and this required to update and specify the information models related to the different types of licenses supported by the platform, depicted in Figure 4. In detail the updates are: (i) Inclusion of the *secretKey* field to use during the validation; (ii) The specification of the instance and time-based licenses.

Figure 4: Software License information model.

Network Applications can be chained together using VSBs. In Figure 5 we detail the information model. The extension to this information element was introduced in D2.3 [5], with the inclusion of *RuntimeActions* which allow to define closed-control loop lifecycle management actions to be performed by the VITAL-5G platform (we refer to D2.3 [5] and D1.3 [2] for further details regarding the closed-control support at the platform level). In Figure 6 we further formalize the information model of the *RuntimeAction*, as originally proposed in D2.3 [5].

Figure 5: Vertical Service Blueprint information model.

Figure 6: RuntimeAction information model.

In VITAL-5G we use Experiment and TestCase Blueprints (ExpBs and TCBs) to model the experiments to be executed on the platform in terms of actions to be executed and KPIs to be measured. In Figure 7 we represent the information model of the TCB, which is used to determine the scripts to be executed during the experiment run configuration, execution and reset phases. The information model of this blueprint was originally established in D2.3 [5], and we refer to this deliverable for further details about the specific fields.

Figure 7: TestCaseBlueprint information model.

ExpBs allow to associate TCBs to specific VSBs and to define the KPIs to be automatically collected and evaluated by the VITAL-5G platform. In Figure 8 we depict the information model associated with this blueprint.

Figure 8: Experiment Blueprint information model.

As in the case of vertical services, experiments can be customized through the establishment of Experiment Descriptors (ExpDs), which allow to determine specific values for the thresholds of the KPIs to be validated, and to establish concrete values for the input parameters of the TestCases. The information model of the ExpDs, originally established in D2.3 [5] is depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Experiment Descriptor information model.

3 VITAL-5G Platform User Guide

The following User Guide is a QuickStart manual concerning the VITAL-5G platform providing 3rd party experimenters providing a quick overview of the basic functionalities of the platform and how they can onboard Network Applications, execute experiments, manage their vertical services and how to compile the available data for their reporting purposes.

3.1 Network Application Onboarding

The VITAL-5G platform enforces a role-based access control mechanism, and therefore every user needs to have credentials in order to access the platform services. 3rd party experimenters shall receive their credentials after completing the 3rd party onboarding process described in the 3rd party experimenters' section of the VITAL-5G website¹.

After the user has received his/her credentials then they need to login on the platform through the page displayed in Figure 10.

Figure 10: The VITAL-5G platform login page.

After the correct credentials have been entered, the user can then view the main page of the platform as shown in Figure 11.

¹ <https://www.vital5g.eu/3rd-party-experimenters-participation/>

Figure 11: The VITAL-5G platform main page.

For the user to onboard a Network Application, he/she needs to access the “Design Experiment” section by clicking on the corresponding button. The user will then be led to the page shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Experiment Design page.

After accessing the “Design Experiment” section, in order to upload a Network Application Blueprint the user needs to first access the “Network Applications” page by pressing the corresponding button leading to the page shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: The "Network Applications" section of the VITAL-5G platform where users can view uploaded Network Applications and onboard Network Application Blueprints.

The user can then upload their own Network Application by clicking the onboard button and following the wizard instructions as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: The Network Application Blueprint onboarding wizard.

The user then needs to simply upload the Network Application Package, containing the Network Application Blueprint, the Software Licenses, etc. as detailed in D2.2 [4], and the corresponding VNF files and the onboarding procedure will be completed. The platform also contains a Network Application validator that will check for any syntax errors and device availability and notify the user if an error exists. After a successful onboarding process, the user will be able to see their own Network Applications in the page in Figure 13. Through the menu page

shown in Figure 12, users can upload VSBs, VNFs and manage all the elements before launching their experiments.

In order for the user to upload their VSB, they need to navigate to the menu shown in Figure 12 and press on the "Vertical Service Blueprint" blueprint which will then lead to the section shown in Figure 15 where the user can launch the wizard shown in Figure 16.

Id	Name	Testbed	Version	View	Delete	Force delete
7627bbdf-2610-4dab-beff-80d5bae7fbfb	NXW IoT Event and Alert and Fault detection	ATHENS	1.0			
046ad57b-4104-4c16-b499-b6e7a64d5f13	Vertical service 1 Remote vessel monitoring	ANTWERP1.0				
3ad777c0-624a-4b25-a7f6-048007254cdb	VS9 service	GALATI	1.0			
6e8629b9-359f-43fe-8d8c-760664faf4b2	VS9 service - CHARMED	GALATI	1.0			

Figure 15: The "Vertical Service Blueprints" section of the VITAL-5G platform where users can view uploaded VSBs and onboard VSBs through the wizard shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: The wizard that allows users to upload their own Vertical Service Blueprints.

Through this intuitive wizard, users can upload their own Blueprints alongside the NSDs and define the access level of the VSB, the testbed the user wants to experiment on, the metrics that the user wants to extract (including infrastructure metrics and relevant KPIs to the experiment) as well as any specific platform components relevant to the VSB. The VSBs are also verified at the syntax level by internal tools developed by the consortium for the platform.

For the platform to load the correct parameters for the experiment to be launched, users need to navigate to the wizard for onboarding the Experiment Blueprints. The wizard is accessible through the menu in Figure 12 after the user has selected the “Experiments Blueprints” option where they will be led to the wizard for uploading their experiment blueprints by selecting the “Onboard” option on the top left side of the screen as shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: The Experiment Blueprint onboarding wizard.

Through this wizard, the user can provide the general information for the experiment blueprint which will help define it uniquely and make it easier to identify, the associated VSB and the metrics associated with the experiment. The wizard is designed to automate the process as much as possible and provide users with a comfortable experience with no prior specialized knowledge being necessary.

3.2 Vertical Service Management

After onboarding the Vertical Service through the “Design Experiment” section functions, users can now proceed to launch an instance of their Vertical Service (VS) and manage its elements. To launch the Vertical Service instance, users must navigate to the Platform’s main menu, as shown in Figure 11, and go to the “Manage VS Instances” page by clicking on the corresponding button. This will lead users to the VS Instances page as shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Vertical Service Instance management page.

From here, users need to click on the “Add new instance button” which will then lead them to the popup shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Vertical Service Instance request pop-up.

The vertical service instance request pop-up allows experiments to give the name of the vertical service the wish to instantiate, a description, choose the appropriate Vertical Service Descriptor (VSD), the access level they wish

(Public, Private or Restricted) which will provide different levels of visibility and accessibility of the service by other Platform users in various levels and the corresponding IMSIs.

After the successful submission, the vertical service instance will appear in the catalogue as shown in Figure 18. From here the user can view the elements of the vertical instance, terminate the instance or delete it entirely from the Platform through the appropriate buttons displayed on the top of the table. By clicking the view button on any vertical instance, will display the ID, name, status, target site, description and Tenant ID of the service as well as the associated descriptor with access to the URLs of the Infrastructure Monitoring, Service Monitoring and Network monitoring as shown from an example vertical service instance in Figure 20.

The screenshot displays the 'Instance Details' page in the VITAL 5G platform. On the left is a navigation menu with options: Home, Site Information, Back, Dashboard, Blueprints, Descriptors, VS Instances, and Run Experiment. The main content area shows a table with the following data:

Field	Value
Id	ce1c667c-cbce-4195-aca1-282295d062a2
Name	test-monitoring-5
Status	INSTANTIATED
Target Sites	GALATI
Description	test
Tenant Id	
Vertical service descriptor	cffc5d48-29b6-4057-a1ce-b5d595cc58a9
Infrastructure Monitoring Url	http://172.28.18.70:3000/d/ffoAkiO4z/ce1c667c-cbce-4195-aca1-282295d062a2_infrastructure
Service Monitoring Url	
Network Monitoring Url	http://172.28.18.70:3000/d/A3A0z5wVk/ce1c667c-cbce-4195-aca1-282295d062a2_network

At the bottom of the table, there is a red button labeled 'Create Experiment'.

Figure 20: Example of Vertical Service Instance details.

Users can directly launch an experiment from this screen. Details of experiment execution and reporting are part of Section 3.3.

By clicking on any of the Monitoring URLs, users can view the Grafana² panels associated with the VS instance and see real-time metrics feedback. An example of such a Grafana panel pertaining to network latency from the Romanian testbed is shown in Figure 21.

² <https://grafana.com/>

Figure 21: Grafana panel extracting network metrics (network latency) from the Romanian testbed.

3.3 Experiment execution and reporting

After an instance has been successfully created, users can now proceed with executing an experiment and generate reports.

An experiment can be launched in two ways:

1. By launching directly from the “Instance Details” page for each Vertical Service as shown in Figure 20.
2. By going to the “Request Experiments” section of the Platform through the main menu as shown in Figure 11.

By going to the “Request Experiments” section of the platform (as shown in Figure 22), the user is then called to upload their experiment descriptor and launch a new experiment.

Figure 22: The "Request Experiments" section of the VITAL-5G platform.

The “Experiment Descriptor” tab allows users to submit the elements of the descriptor (Descriptor Metadata, KPIs and Test Case Configuration) after clicking on the Onboard button which will launch the wizard as shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: The onboarding wizard for the experiment descriptor on the VITAL-5G platform.

After onboarding the experiment descriptor users can navigate to the “New Experiment” tab where they are able to schedule a new experiment as shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Scheduling a new experiment on the VITAL-5G platform.

From thereon, users can view the experiment progress and access reports with the results of the experiment. An example of such a report can be seen in Figure 25.

Analysis & Validation Results

Figure 25: Example of a report generated with the help of the VITAL-5G platform.

4 Final version of the VITAL-5G Experimentation Platform

4.1 High-level Design & Software Components

The VITAL-5G Platform is the entry point offering the VITAL-5G service design, and experimentation services on top of the infrastructure of the three 5G-enabled testbeds of the project. As described in D1.2 [1] (and further evolved in D1.3 [2]), this Platform enables:

- **Network Application and Vertical Service design and management:** The VITAL-5G Platform offers a catalogue of Network Applications and Vertical Services which can be used by users/ 3rd parties to onboard and possibly share applications with automated management of the orchestration descriptors.
- **Automated monitoring configuration, monitoring data retrieval and visualization:** The Platform leverages the metrics described in the different Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprints to automatically configure the monitoring of the Platform to extract the metrics from the VITAL-5G testbeds.
- **5G Network Slice Management capabilities:** the Platform holds a 5G slice catalogue with 5G slice lifecycle management capabilities. In this sense, the Platform uses the 5G slice profile established in the Network Applications and Vertical Services to allocate a 5G Slice to the service, or possibly dynamically create one based on the testbed.
- **Experiment execution and report generation support:** the VITAL-5G Platform supports the execution of experiments and the visualization of the experiment reports, with the validation of the experiment KPIs through the Portal Web GUI.
- **AI-based service troubleshooting:** The introduction of the AI-based analytics module enabled automated service analysis through AI-based algorithms, providing enhanced experiment reports and supporting automated closed-control loops actions.
- **ML/Analytics toolkit for data postprocessing:** The VITAL-5G platform offers AI/ML capabilities for service data post-processing, which aims to identify outlying behaviour/abnormal data with respect to monitored KPIs.
- **Automated service lifecycle management capabilities:** The VITAL-5G automatically manages the lifecycle of the network services associated with the Network Applications, with validation of the available licenses.

As described in D2.1 [3] and evolved in D2.2 [4] and D2.3 [5], the VITAL-5G Platform is composed by a set of components interacting most of the times through a REST-based interface, to provide a specific set of functionalities as detailed in Table 2 and mentioned previously. The interactions of the aforementioned components are shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26: VITAL-5G Platform Components

4.2 Software Components & Evolution

The components mentioned in the previous section have either been completely new and developed within the VITAL-5G project or reused based on previous projects and evolved during the project's lifetime. Furthermore, minor, major and/or final releases have been described in previous deliverables. The following table (Table 2) summarizes which of the aforementioned software components are new, have been updated/improved within the projects and compares with their last version/release.

Table 2: Platform component updates compared to (a) previous projects and (b) previous version/release.

Platform component	Description	Justification (New/Reused) compared to previous projects.	Updates since last deliverable/release?
Portal web GUI	Graphical interface providing unified access to VITAL-5G Platform.	Reused from 5G-EVE but revamped completely to fit the purpose of the project. More specifically, the VITAL-5G GUI, will provide access to users to all the backend functionalities and tools of the VITAL-5G platform to design their experiments. The goal is to provide an intent-based service where internal and 3 rd -party users can conveniently select experiments, the Network Applications that they would like to use from the Network Application catalogue or upload their own Network Application for testing and the required service blueprints. The main features that the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI offers are: Implementation of Access Control using KeyCloak integration as described in the relevant component, an improved Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprint filtering using a variety of parameters (testbed, use case or status) depending on the user's needs, advanced testcase blueprint management and updated experiment descriptors, implementation of the experiment Life Cycle Manager, improved monitoring capabilities as well as improved 34visualization of the vertical service blueprints.	The updates pertain mostly to QoE improvements and the updated connectivity to components featured in Drop III (e.g., license manager) as well as addition of functionalities such as removal of experiment through dedicated buttons.
Network Applications, Services & Experiments Catalogue	Catalogue and logic of VITAL-5G Open Online Repository, holding the Network Application, Vertical Service and Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors. Interacts with the testbed NFVO catalogue to manage the network services and orchestration related descriptors.	Uses 5G EVE Portal Catalogue as baseline. VITAL-5G contributions targeted: (i) Introduction of the information elements and repositories to support the VITAL-5G Network Application concept; (ii) Update information elements to decouple experiments and vertical services to enable independent lifecycle management operations; (iii) Development of drivers to support Testbed NFVO catalogue management and synchronization; (iv) Update catalogue management workflows to leverage file storage backends (e.g. MinIO [8]); (v) Develop interfaces and update workflows to use	Updated blueprint data models Support for license onboarding

		other VITAL-5G platform modules (i.e. Multi-site inventory, Network Application Validation, etc.).	
Service LCM	Manager to coordinate the instantiation and lifecycle actions of vertical services, interacting with the underlying testbed NFVO and with the different platform modules for: (i) configuration of monitoring metrics; (ii) allocation of the 5G network slice; (iii) control of licenses associated with the Network Applications; (iv) Retrieval of blueprints and descriptors from the Network Applications, Services & Experiments catalogue.	Uses 5G EVE Service LCM as baseline. VITAL-5G contributions will target: (i) Interface and workflow updated decouple experiments and vertical services to enable independent lifecycle management operations; (ii) Development of drivers to support Testbed NFVO LCM; (iii) Develop interfaces and update workflows to use other VITAL-5G platform modules (i.e. Multi-site inventory, Monitoring platform, Multi-site 5G slice inventory etc.).	Automated License validation Enhanced support for closed-control loops
License Manager	Component to store and validate Network Application licenses.	New component; designed and developed in the VITAL-5G project.	Fully implemented for D2.4
Access Control	Entity to authorize users' access to VITAL-5G services, based on roles and user use case mapping.	Reused from 5G-EVE but revamped completely to fit the purpose of the project. The Access control system in the 5G-EVE project is based on a Dockerized Keycloak service, an open-source IAM solution. The GUI and backend services (i.e., experiment-lcm, multi-site-inventory, NetworkApplicationCatalog, NetworkApplicationValidator, service-lcm) interact with the Access control component and limit system access to authorized users through RBAC (Role-Based Access Control). Roles are defined at Keycloak's realm level, including Experimenter, Network Application Developer, Platform Admin, Platform Technician, Testbed Admin, T&L Site Infrastructure Manager, and Vertical Service Provider. Additional granularity is achieved by assigning extra attributes to the user's access token for each Use Case (UC1, UC2, UC3).	No updates. Fully developed 'n D2.3.

Slice Manager and Inventory³	Provides the centralized catalogue of 5G slices available for each testbed, and exposes the interfaces for slice allocation for the rest of the components of the VITAL-5G platform.	New component entirely developed within VITAL-5G.	All features presented in D2.3 developed and integrated. Decision-making algorithm for slice selection implemented and integrated.
Multi-site Inventory	Centralized inventory with information on all testbeds.	New component; designed and developed in the VITAL-5G project.	No updates. Fully developed in D2.3
Monitoring Platform (Centralized)	Interfaces with the per-testbed monitoring agents for the configuration of the monitoring metrics and collects the metrics coming from the agents through specialized message queues. Furthermore, provides monitoring storing and querying capabilities through an ELK-like deployment	New component; designed and developed in the VITAL-5G project.	Minor updates have been made in the code to incorporate necessary changes identified during the VITAL-5G platform integration phase: i) topic names include the VM reference, and ii) all payload fields converted to string values.
Experiment LCM	Manager to coordinate the service testing and experiment procedures.	Uses 5G EVE Experiment LCM as baseline. VITAL-5G contributions will target: (i) Interface and workflow updated to decouple experiments and vertical services to enable independent lifecycle management operations; (ii) Development of drivers to support enhanced test execution mechanisms; ((iii) Develop interfaces and update workflows to use other VITAL-5G platform modules (i.e. Multi-site inventory, monitoring platform,); (iv) Updates to use new Testcase Blueprint and descriptor information elements.	No updates. Fully developed in D2.3
Network Application Validator	Tool to verify the correct deployment of a Network Application in the target testbed at onboarding time. Incorporates the originally described as Blueprint Validation tool, responsible for the verification of the blueprints' format during their onboarding	New component, that incorporates the Blueprint Validation Tool (from 5G-EVE). With respect to the latter, it was introduced in 5G-EVE, but revamped completely to fit the purpose of the VITAL-5G project. The validator from 5G-EVE was a command-line tool (a jar file) with limited functionality: static validation of the syntax of a blueprint. For this	Experiment termination as part of the Network Application instantiation and experiment lifecycle workflow

³ It should be noted that in previous releases this component was referred as slice inventory. Since it also provides management capabilities, we renamed the module to highlight the update"

		project, it has been re-packaged as a web application to be part of the Network Application Validator. Besides validation of blueprint syntax, it also performs basic validation of IoT data used by the Network Application. Concerning the other Network Application Validator aspects, new components include OpenAPI-based REST interfaces for interaction with other components; validation of sensor data in the testbed facilities (via interaction with multi-site inventory); dynamic KPI monitoring and validation from the 5G testbed.	Validation of the user roles to access the validator endpoints.
Intent-based requests manager	Tool to simplify the request of services and experiments. Support of Network Applications and integration with VITAL-5G platform.	The Intent-based requests manager is based on the 5G-EVE intent-based tool, but with several major enhancements. It provides an alternative mechanism to define VITAL-5G experiments, adopting an approach based on the natural language. Features include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation of 5G-EVE intent-based tool for use cases and models in VITAL-5G • Redesign of Intent-based tool GUI • Interaction with Experiment LCM for triggering experiments • Integration with Access Control 	This component was targeted for development in the last release.
Results analytics	Component to analyze the collected KPIs and evaluate the service performance.	Component reused from 5G EVE. Updated with real-time operation and support for generating triggers for the LCM closed-loop control mechanism.	Bug fixes and updates to the information models have been performed, as the result of the internal integration activities and specifically the Monitoring platform.
AI-based diagnostics	Component to produce performance insights on the basis of the collected KPIs	Component reused from 5G EVE. Updated with real-time operation and support for generating triggers for the LCM closed-loop control mechanism.	No updates since D2.3
ML/Analytics toolkit	Component that allows the user to conduct <i>ad hoc</i> analysis of experiment-related network and infrastructure KPIs using a set of machine learning (ML) approaches for outlier detection, allowing users to train their own models.	New component, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project, based also on Intelligent proprietary work for ML components.	Functionality originally developed for VA3 Network Application (description in D2.3 [5] targeting D2.4 for final release), but

			incorporated as a VITAL-5G Platform component.
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Complementing the information provided in Table 2, Table 3 provides further details on the licensing and links to the relevant repositories.

Table 3: Platform component access and links to repositories.

Platform component	Access (OPENSOURCE vs. CLOSED SOURCE)	Links to repositories
Portal web GUI	OPEN SOURCE (Apache v2.0)	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/portal-web-gui
Network Applications, Services & Experiments Catalogue	OPEN SOURCE (Apache v2.0)	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository
Service LCM	OPEN SOURCE (Apache v2.0)	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/service-lcm
License Manager	OPEN SOURCE (Apache v2.0)	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/license-manager
Access Control	OPEN SOURCE (Apache v2.0)	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/access-control
Slice Inventory	CLOSED SOURCE	N/A
Multi-site Inventory	OPEN SOURCE (Apache v2.0)	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/multi-site-inventory
Monitoring Platform (Centralized)	CLOSED SOURCE	N/A
Experiment LCM	OPEN SOURCE (Apache v2.0)	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/experiment-lcm
Network Application Validator	OPEN SOURCE (Apache v2.0)	https://gitlab.slicenet.oteresearch.gr/vital-5g_platform/blueprint-validator
Intent-based requests manager	OPEN SOURCE (Apache v2.0)	https://gitlab.slicenet.oteresearch.gr/vital-5g_platform/ibn-manager
Results analytics	CLOSED SOURCE	Proprietary, and as such is released in binary format. Available at https://gitlab.slicenet.oteresearch.gr/vital-5g_platform/results-analytics
AI-based diagnostics	CLOSED SOURCE	Proprietary, and as such is released in binary format. Available at https://gitlab.slicenet.oteresearch.gr/vital-5g_platform/ai-diagnostics
ML/Analytics toolkit	CLOSED SOURCE	N/A

4.2.1 Portal Web GUI

The Portal Web GUI is the graphical environment that allows users to interface with the VITAL-5G Platform in order to onboard Network Applications, Manage VSs, execute experiments and explore experiment results.

4.2.1.1 Final Release Features

The early-drop version of the VITAL-5G Platform’s Portal Web GUI, described in deliverable D2.2 [4], was a revamped version of the Web GUI developed as part of 5G-EVE project [7] and was extended to cover the upload, visualization, and management of Network Application Blueprints. Additionally, the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI is responsible for the KPIs visualization of the experiments conducted at each T&L trial site. We follow an agile interaction design to achieve practical and pragmatic design, short development cycles, and dynamic designs that are responsive to changing needs.

In Figure 11, we provide a visual representation of the current state of the VITAL-5G GUI main page with the following features implemented in the transition from the early drop to the last full release:

- Implementation of the Access Control module using KeyCloak integration
- Improved Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB) filtering per testbed, use case or status according to the individual user's needs)
- TestCase Blueprint (TCB) Management and updated Experiment Descriptors
- Implementation of the Experiment Lifecycle Manager (LCM) management pages, which provides:
 - Visualization of list of experiments
 - Trigger instantiation/termination of experiments
 - Visualization of experiment details
- Updated monitoring capabilities added links and frames mapped to Grafana dashboards.
- Improved visualization of VSBs in terms of graphs and linking to Network Application structure.
- **[NEW]** In the final release, we provided additional support tools for 3rd party users including templates for uploading Vertical Services Instances with as little trouble as possible. One of the tools is the Network Application validator, released with the final operational version of the platform, that allows users to run checks in their 3rd party Network Application before uploading it on the platform.
- **[NEW]** Lastly, various QoE improvements have been implemented such as easier access to the Monitoring Panels and Service Instantiation. The GUI has been improved continuously during the transition of the platform from Drop II to Drop III through trial runs at each integration and E2E testing meeting, identifying issues and resolving them in dedicated sprints.

4.2.1.2 Software Architecture

The component diagram for the VITAL-5G GUI is presented in Figure 27. The web-based GUI provides users with the ability to explore the catalogue of accessible Network Applications and configure suitable filters. It offers a graphical representation of the Network Applications, showcasing their individual components, internal connections, and external links, including the integration with the 5G network and its associated requirements and slice profiles. Furthermore, the GUI incorporates tools and wizards to streamline the process of creating a Network Application Package, guiding users through the necessary steps to add all the essential elements and populate various fields within the Network Application blueprint. Through the web GUI, users have the option to download the schemas of the Network Application blueprint. This functionality aims to assist in the offline creation and definition of new Network Applications. By downloading the schemas, users can work on defining and designing Network Applications without requiring an active online connection.

Additionally, the web GUI enables interaction with the Network Applications Validator. This Validator serves the purpose of verifying the accuracy and proper formatting of the Network Application package and Network Application blueprint during the onboarding process. It ensures that the provided package and blueprint align with the features, capabilities, and devices available in the target testbed.

Figure 27: VITAL-5G GUI component diagram.

4.2.1.3 APIs and Interfaces

The GUI does not have exposed APIs, but rather connects with the (Centralised) Monitoring Platform that is in charge of collecting the Network and Service KPIs and displaying them on-demand for the user, the Experiment and Service LCM, the Network Applications, Services and Experiments Catalogue as well as the Blueprints Validation tool which is integral for Quality of Experience (QoE) for 3rd party users.

4.2.1.4 Software Assets

The GUI is released under an Apache 2 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository⁴. It was generated using Angular CLI⁵, version 9.1.7. The environment setup requires the installation of nodejs, the Angular modules, the project dependencies as well as the development server. Notably, Angular applications are modular and thus Angular comes with its own modularity system called NgModules. NgModules are containers for a cohesive block of code dedicated to an application domain, a workflow, or a closely related set of capabilities. They can contain components, service providers, and other code files whose scope is defined by the containing NgModule.

⁴ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/portal-web-gui

⁵ <https://github.com/angular/angular-cli>

Every Angular application has at least one NgModule class, the root module, which is conventionally named AppModule and resides in a file named app.module.ts. To launch the VITAL-5G GUI module the application needs to be bootstrapped from the root NgModule. Angular loads as a collection of JavaScript modules which can be thought in the context of library modules. Each Angular library name begins with the @angular prefix. They can be installed with the node package manager npm and parts of them can be imported with JavaScript import statements.

The install folder in the module repository⁶ contains precise installation instructions which allow any user or developer to build and execute this module.

4.2.2 Network Applications, Services & Experiment Catalogue – Open Online Repository

As described in D2.1 [3], this component offers the Network Application, Service and Experiment catalogue management services of the VITAL-5G platform through REST-based northbound API, which is used by the Portal Web GUI (see Section 4.2.1) and the rest of the components to onboard, retrieve and delete the different blueprints and descriptors associated with the Network Applications, Vertical Services and Experiments. Furthermore, this module is responsible for guaranteeing the synchronization of the three VITAL-5G site NFVO catalogues, and the platform internal database. Internally this module interacts with:

- i. Access Control module, to authenticate and authorize the request and retrieve user information data;
- ii. Network Application Validator, to determine if the blueprint is valid in terms of formatting and the correspondent devices are onboarded on the platform;
- iii. Multi-site inventory, to fetch the VITAL-5G site NFVO endpoints and credentials;
- iv. License Manager module to onboard the licenses already available in the Network Application package.

4.2.2.1 Final Release Features

The main functionality introduced in this module this final release is support for the automated license management of the platform. For this reason, this release of the module includes support for onboarding and deletion of license keys during the onboarding and deletion of Network Application packages. The final list of features supported by this module, built on top of the functionalities described in D2.3 [5] and D2.2 [4], is as follows:

- **[NEW]** Automated License Management: Creation and deletion of Network Application licenses as part of the Network Application onboarding and deletion workflows.
- Access Control integration: Validation of the user roles (e.g., Network Application Developer, Vertical Service Provider, etc) to execute the management actions as established in D1.2 [1]. Validation of the descriptor ownership and use case mapping to authorize request.
- Automated Network Application Validation: Leverage the *Network Application Validator* module to provide automated Network Application Blueprint syntax validation and verify availability of the required devices in the VITAL-5G targeted site.
- File storage backend support: Integration of MinIO [8] for enhanced file storage support, and ease access to Network Application package assets (i.e., API documentation, licenses, etc.).
- VITAL-5G site NFVO catalogue management: Support of site NFVO VNF Package and NSD catalogue management via per-site plugins, with *Multi-site inventory* integration for NFVO information retrieval.
- Support for Network Application, Service and Experiment catalogue: REST based interface supporting onboarding, querying and deletion of Network Application packages, Vertical Service Blueprint and Descriptors and Experiment Blueprints.

⁶ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/

- Support for Test Case definition and management: Management of the Test Case Blueprints and Descriptors, which provide the actions to execute during an experiment and to reset the environment once the experiment finishes.

4.2.2.2 Software Architecture

In Figure 28, we depict the software architecture of this module, highlighting the sub-component introduced on this release for the automated license management. As described in D2.1 [3], D2.2 [4] and D2.3 [5], this module is a Spring-Boot based Java application. The logic implemented by each internal module is as follows:

- REST Controller: As described in D2.2 [4], this module enables REST endpoints for the catalogue management operations, and performs an format and access control validation before forwarding the request to the catalogue service module. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.nbi* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project.
- Catalogue Service: This module performs in-depth validation of the request together with the *Network Application Validator* module, and interacts with the VITAL-5G site through the NFVO Sync Manager module for the management of the VNF Packages and NSDs associated with the Network Applications and VSBs. Moreover, this module interacts with the JPA-based repositories for the management of the database associated entries, and with the *File Storage Client* for the management of the files associated with the Network Applications. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.services* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project. The first-full-version release added support for access control verification, and integration with the *Network Application Validator* module.
- JPA-Based repositories: This module mediates between the Catalogue Service and the database providing simplified interfaces for the management of the database records. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.repos* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project.
- NFVO Synch Manager and NFVO Catalogue Service: These two modules mediate between the internal catalogue components and the NFVO VNF and NSD catalogues of the VITAL-5G testbeds, providing a simplified and unified interface, and automated syncing the NFVO catalogue based on the Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprint catalogue operations. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.sbi* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project. This release includes per-site plugins implementing the site-specific management logic (based on OSM), and the interaction with the *Multi-site inventory* for site NFVO information retrieval.
- SQL database: The database created to support the registries associated with the different catalogues.
- File Storage Client and MINIO: MinIO is a high-performance and high-availability object storage platform which is used to store and manage the files associated with a Network Application (i.e., Network Application package and blueprint, licenses, software documentation, etc). The File Storage Client, implements the logic to interact with MinIO to sync the catalogue management operations with the storage backend.
- Multi-site inventory client: Implements a REST client to consume the *Multi-site inventory* API to retrieve the testbed capabilities, and the NFVO information.
- Network Application Validator client: Implements a REST client to consume the *Network Application Validator* API to validate the Network Application blueprint syntax and validate device availability in the targeted site.
- License Manager client: Implements the service and the REST client to interact with the *License Manager*, in order to trigger the creation and deletion of the licenses associated with a Network Application package. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.sbi.license* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project.

Figure 28: Open online repository internal software architecture.

4.2.2.3 APIs and Interfaces

The API of this module is described in D2.2 [4], and the full specification is available in OpenAPI format⁷. No changes were introduced on this release on the API.

4.2.2.4 Software Assets

This module is released as open source, using an Apache 2.0 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository⁸.

4.2.3 Service LCM

As described in D2.1 [3], this component provides the service lifecycle management capabilities (i.e., instantiation, termination, scaling and querying), via a REST-based interface. The submodules inside this module are therefore responsible for implementing the logic for the Vertical Service Instance management, interfacing with:

- i. *Monitoring platform* for the management of the monitoring metrics to be retrieved;
- ii. *Results analytics/ AI-based diagnostics*, to determine service instantiation and termination;
- iii. Interaction with *Multi-site slice inventory* for the creation or association of the 5G slices to the service;
- iv. the VITAL-5G site NFVO for the lifecycle management of the Network Services and Network functions;
- v. License manager, for Network Application license key verification and usage update. In order to function properly, this module holds internally databases containing the records associated with the vertical services instances and implements the finite state machine described in D2.1 [3].

⁷https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository/-/blob/main/API/VITAL-5G%20open%20repository%20OpenAPI.json

⁸ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository

4.2.3.1 Final Release Features

In this release, the focus has been set in the functionalities related to: (i) AI-based control loops, with further integration for 5G Network Slice and Network Service scaling procedure; (ii) Automated license management, enabling license key validation during the service instantiation and scaling, and usage update during service termination. For completeness we report here the full set of features supported by this module, adding the features introduced by this release on top of the features reported in D2.2 [4] and D2.3 [5].

- **[NEW]** Automated License validation: Integration with the License Manager module, to enable license key validation and usage update during the service instantiation, modification and termination phases.
- **[UPDATE]** Support for vertical service scaling/modification for closed-loop automation: Implementation of REST-based interface (to be used by other platform modules) and logic to enable automated service scaling. Implementation of scaling policies catalogue and logic for automated service scaling.
- Access control validation: Integration with the *Access control* module for role and user use case verification.
- Vertical Service Lifecycle Management: Service instantiation, termination and querying with creation and deletion of associated instance records. Integration with *service catalogue* for blueprint and descriptor usage update.
- Automated configuration of Network Application and Vertical Service metrics: Integration with the *Monitoring Platform* to enable automated creation and deletion of the monitoring metrics associated with the vertical services and network applications.
- Automated management of Network Slices: Integration with *Multi-site slice inventory* for the retrieval or provisioning of network slices depending on the site capabilities.
- VITAL-5G site NFVO Lifecycle Management integration: Automated Network Service Lifecycle management capabilities on the three VITAL-5G sites, including NFVO information retrieval from the *Multi-site inventory*.

4.2.3.2 Software Architecture

The internal software architecture of this module is depicted in Figure 29, highlighting the components introduced or updated in this final release.

Figure 29: Service LCM internal software architecture.

The functionality implemented by each sub-module, the correspondent package and the modifications performed in this final release is as follows:

- **REST Controller:** As described in D2.1 [1], this module implements the REST server responsible for receiving and performing an initial validation of the incoming request in terms of syntax, authorization and overall completeness of the requested action. After a successful validation this sub-module forwards the request to the Service LCM Engine. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.nbi* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project. For the final release this sub-module was updated to enhance the vertical service modification/scaling procedures., and to enable the passing of license keys.
- **Service LCM Engine:** This sub-module processes all the service lifecycle management requests, validating the messages, creating instance specific service managers, and forwarding the messages towards the specific manager. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.engine* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project. For the final release this module was extended to support the new vertical service modification and scaling requests.
- **Vertical Service Instance (VSI) Manager:** As described in D2.1 [1], this module is responsible for the lifecycle management requests for one specific service instance, interacting with a set of southbound services interfacing with other VITAL-5G platform components or testbed agents. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.manager* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project. This module was extended for this final release with the inclusion of the logic to interface with updated NFVO Service for the service scaling and with the Slice inventory for the slice modification.
- **VSI Record Manager:** This module mediates with the Postgres DB [\[1\]](#) to manage the service instance records. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.repo* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.

- Open online repository Service & Client: As established in D2.2 [2], these two modules implement the logic for the retrieval of the Network Applications and Vertical Service Blueprints and Descriptors from the *Network Application, Services and Experiments Catalogue* via a REST client. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.catalogue* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- NFVO Service & NFVO client: As established in D2.2 [2], these modules mediate between the VSI Manager and the specific testbed NFVO supporting a unified interface for the network service lifecycle management operations. This release added support CPU and RAM scaling in support of the vertical service scaling procedures. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.nfvo* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- Multi-site inventory service & client: This module is used to mediate between the internal components of the service lifecycle management, and the *Multi-site inventory*. In this release this submodule supports the retrieval of the testbed NFVO information and slicing capabilities. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.siteinventory* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- Multi-site 5G slice inventory service and client: Implements the client for the *Multi-site 5G slice inventory* which enables the allocation/de-allocation of the required slices and the attachment of UEs to 5G slices. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.sliceinventory* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- VSI RuntimeAction service: As detailed in D2.3 [5], the objective of this module is to trigger automated vertical service lifecycle management actions (e.g., service scaling, transport network re-configuration, etc) according to the runtime actions configured on the VSB to support closed-control loops. For this, this module subscribes to the correspondent topics on the *Monitoring platform*, and automatically triggers the requested action through the VSI LCM Engine. We refer to Section 4 for more details regarding the workflow. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.control* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.

4.2.3.3 APIs and Interfaces

The API of this module is described in D2.2 [4] and the full specification is available in OpenAPI format⁹. In order to enable passing License keys at instantiation time, the API was updated to include a field where the experimenter may provide the licenses for the different Network Applications. Furthermore, the API to enable service modifications (i.e., 5G Network Slice modification, Network service scaling) has been extended and enabled on the northbound interface.

4.2.3.4 Software Assets

This module is released as open source, using an Apache 2.0 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository¹⁰.

4.2.4 Licence Manager

This release of the VITAL-5G includes the license management and validation functionalities of the platform, with the release of the License Manager module, which is responsible for: (i) Storing and managing the licenses associated with the Network Applications; (ii) Keep an updated status of the usage of the Network Application licenses; (iii) Validate the Network Application and Vertical Service lifecycle management operations (e.g. Instantiation requests).

⁹ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository/-/blob/main/API/VITAL-5G%20open%20repository%20OpenAPI.json

¹⁰ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/service-lcm

4.2.4.1 Final Release Features

This module has been entirely released as part of the final release. This release mainly covers updates and bug fixes reported during the internal integration tests and experimentation. For completeness we report here the full list of features of this module (see D2.3 [5]):

- Access control module for the validation and authentication of the user credentials;
- Integration with Results Analytics for signalling experiment creation and termination procedures
- Automated Monitoring configuration: Integration with *Monitoring Platform* module for the creation of experiment specific metrics
- Automated execution of experiment scripts: Automated execution of DAY2 actions for experiment preparation, execution and cleaning through NFVO client with support for the execution of experiment scripts.

4.2.4.2 Software Architecture

In Figure 30 we depict the internal software architecture of this module, as originally established in D2.1 [3]. The functionality of the internal modules shown in the picture is as follows:

- **REST Controller:** The REST controller is the module which implements the REST server of this module and is responsible for exposing the API described in Section 4.2.4.3, which offers an interface to enable the onboarding of Network Application licenses, Validation of a lifecycle management request, and update the usage of a specific license key. As depicted in Figure 30, this module interfaces with the Network Application Developer to enable the management of the available license keys, and with the Service LCM to expose services to validate and update the usage of the license keys performing initial validation and access control on the incoming requests.
- **License Storage Service:** This module is responsible for managing the catalogue of license keys associated with the Network Applications. In this sense, this module further processes and validates the incoming license catalogue management operations, interfacing with the JPA based repositories for the associated database records.
- **License Validation Service:** This module implements the logic related to the license key validation and license usage, interfacing with the JPA based database for retrieval and managing of the associated records.
- **JPA-based repositories:** This module mediates between the module services and the database, abstracting the database specific operations.

Figure 30: License Manager Software Architecture.

4.2.4.3 APIs and Interfaces

The OpenAPI definition of the API exposed by this module is available in https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/license-manager, and is depicted in Figure 31. As described in the figure, the endpoints exposed allow to: (i) Create a License; (ii) Update the usage of a license; (iii) Validate the lifecycle management operation. Figure 32 details the input parameters required for the License Validation and Figure 33 shows a validation example response.

Figure 31: License Manager API.

Name	Description
networkAppId * required	networkAppId
string(\$uuid) (path)	<input type="text" value="networkAppId"/>
request * required	request
object (body)	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> Example Value Model </div> <pre style="background-color: #2e3436; color: #eeeeec; padding: 5px;"> { "licenseKey": "string", "operationType": "NETWORK_APPLICATION_INSTANTIATION", "serviceInstanceId": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6" } </pre>
	Parameter content type <input type="text" value="application/json"/>

Figure 32: License Validation Request.

200	License validation result
	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> Example Value Model </div> <pre style="background-color: #2e3436; color: #eeeeec; padding: 5px;"> { "licenseId": "3fa85f64-5717-4562-b3fc-2c963f66afa6", "successful": true } </pre>

Figure 33: License Validation Response.

4.2.4.4 Software Assets

This module is released with an Apache 2.0 based open-source license, and the code is available in the VITAL-5G software Gitlab repositories¹¹.

4.2.5 Network Application and Blueprint Validation Tool

As presented in D2.1 [3], the Network Application validator is based on a static validator before Network Application runtime together with a dynamic KPI monitoring and validator tool at onboarding/runtime. During the first-full release of the Network Application validator tool, the static validator tool is enhanced and basic dynamic KPI monitoring is implemented with monitoring parameters obtained from the 5G testbed. Its main functionality is to validate the blueprint of the Network Application according to the static features as well as the dynamic 5G network parameters. Figure 34 shows the positioning of the component within the overall tool high level architecture.

4.2.5.1 Final Release Features

The main functionality introduced in this final release of the validator is the support for the termination of the experiment as a result of the monitoring of the KPIs received from the centralized monitoring platform. Also, integration with the Access Control has been accomplished.

The list of features supported by the validator is as follows:

- **[NEW]** Experiment termination: Experiment termination as part of the Network Application instantiation and experiment lifecycle workflow.

¹¹ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/license-manager

- **[NEW]** Access Control integration: Validation of the user roles to access the validator endpoints as established in D1.2 [1]. Use case mapping to authorize request.
- Validation of sensor availability in the facility.
- OpenAPI endpoints for calling the validator for Network Application and Vertical Service blueprints or IoT data validation.
- KPI monitoring and validation for the 5G testbed.
- Deployment of web application in container.

4.2.5.2 Software Architecture

Figure 34: 5G Network Application validator tool high-level architecture.

According to the architecture, the tool performs:

- **Static validation:** The static validator tool receives the Network Application/Vertical Service Blueprints and performs the validation of syntax and devices. If either fails, then the Network Application is not onboarded.
- **Dynamic validation:** Once the Network Application is onboarded and an experiment is triggered, the dynamic KPI monitoring and validation receives data from the deployment/experiment via the centralized monitoring platform. If KPI values fall under a threshold, then a call is made to the experiment LCM to terminate the experiment.

4.2.5.3 APIs and Interfaces

As described in D2.3 [5], the API specification is available in OpenAPI format¹² while an illustration of the API of this module is shown in Figure 35.

¹² https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/blueprint-validator/-/tree/main/API

Network Application Validator API 1.0.0 OAS3

<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/asynccapi/spec/v2.6.0/examples/streetlights-kafka.yml>

Simple API for calling the VITAL-5G Network Application validator

[Contact the developer](#)

default ^

POST `/api/blueprint/validate/syntax` Validate the syntax of the JSON blueprint v

POST `/api/blueprint/validate/sensors` Validate the sensor list of the JSON blueprint v

POST `/api/blueprint/validate` Validate the JSON blueprint v

Schemas ^

Response ←

Figure 35: Network Application validator APIs.

There is no direct use of the API by 3rd parties, as the validator functionality is embedded within the VITAL-5G platform.

4.2.5.4 Software Assets

This module is released with an Apache 2.0 based open-source license, and the code is available in the VITAL-5G software Gitlab repositories¹³.

4.2.6 Experiment LCM

4.2.6.1 Final Release Features

The Experiment Lifecycle Manager (LCM), as described in D2.1 [3], is the component which implements the logic for the creation and execution of experiments to evaluate the Network Applications and services on top of the 5G-enabled infrastructure of the project. The services are offered through a REST-based interface which is used by the experimenters (through the *Portal Web* GUI) to request new experiments, configure and launch their execution, retrieve information on their status and results, and terminate them.

4.2.6.2 Software Architecture

The software architecture of this module is depicted in Figure 36. The description of each sub-module, taken from D2.3 [5], is reported here for completeness:

¹³ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_platform/blueprint-validator/

- **REST Controller:** Implements a REST server supporting the northbound interface of the module enabling experiment management, leveraging the *Access Control* for the authentication and authorization of the incoming request. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.experiment.nbi* package inside *vital-5g experiment-lcm* project. This new release of this internal module added support access control validation.
- **Experiment Execution Coordinator:** Processes all the lifecycle management requests coming from the REST Controller, creating, and interacting with the specific Experiment Instance Managers, which are in charge of the lifecycle management of the single experiment execution, and with the database used for the persistence of experiment data. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.experiment.coordinator* package inside *vital-5g experiment-lcm* project.
- **Experiment Instance Manager:** Handles the lifecycle management of a specific experiment instance following the finite state described in D2.1 [3], and it interacts with the external components of the VITAL-5G Platform. In this release the development focused on the integration of the *Monitoring platform*, *Results Analytics*, and execution of test scripts through the *NFVO client*. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.experiment.manager* package inside the *vital-5g experiment-lcm* project.
- **JPA-based repositories & SQL database:** Hold and provide access to the persistent experiment instance records, containing the information about the experiment instance (i.e., experiment status, vertical service instance id, etc.).
- **Experiment LCM SBI services:** Implement the interaction with the other VITAL-5G platform components: (i) Open online repository client, for the retrieval of Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors (ExpBs and ExpDs); (ii) Service LCM, to retrieve service instance information and lock the instance for experimentation; (iii) Monitoring Client, for the configuration of experiment specific metrics; (iv) Results Analytics Client, to signal the execution and termination of experiments; (v) NFVO client, for the retrieval of network service instance information and execution of test scripts through Day2 actions.

Figure 36: Experiment LCM internal software architecture.

4.2.6.3 APIs and Interfaces

The API definition for this module has been documented in D2.1 [3], D2.2 [4] and D2.3 [5] and is available in OpenAPI format¹⁴.

4.2.6.4 Software Assets

This module is released as open source, using an Apache 2.0 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository.

4.2.7 Access Control

The Access control module is an essential component of the VITAL-5G project, responsible for managing user access and authentication across multiple system components. This module interacts with multiple modules, including the Portal Web GUI, Network Applications, Services & Experiments Catalogue, Service LCM, Experiment LCM, and Network Applications Validator. By relying on Keycloak [9], an Identity and Access Management service, the Access control module securely stores user credentials, generates access tokens, and refreshes them as needed. The module utilizes Role Based Access Control (RBAC) to manage user permissions and access levels within the system. Through its interaction with various components of the VITAL-5G project, the Access control module provides a comprehensive and robust framework for managing user access, ensuring the security and integrity of the system.

4.2.7.1 Final Release Features

This component has been almost entirely released as part of the first-full release version (described in D2.3 [5]). Its features are presented below:

- Token-based authentication enables registered users to obtain an access token based on their role, granting them access to specific resources within the back-end components.
- A "refresh token" is provided, which allows users to obtain a new access token once it expires.
- The access token includes a list of the project's use-cases, providing a finer level of granularity to the Access Control mechanism.
- The Access Control module assigns roles, groups, and custom attributes to users through JSON Web Tokens (JWT), which determine the user's permissions and access levels for specific resources within the VITAL-5G project's back-end components.
- The Access Control module is fully integrated with the Portal Web GUI, vertical service lifecycle management (LCM) and Network Applications Services & Experiment Catalogue for role and user case verification.
- VITAL-5G has implemented an RBAC model by defining roles at the realm level in Keycloak. Upon user registration, these roles are assigned, allowing the creation of isolated groups of applications and users.

4.2.7.2 Software Architecture

The figure below illustrates the general use of access control in the VITAL-5G project, which is a critical component of the system's software architecture.

The process for accessing resources begins when a user attempts to log in to the system through the Portal Web GUI. Keycloak is responsible for handling user authentication upon successful login, Keycloak obtains an access token that is used to request access to the backend resources.

The backend resource (e.g., Network Applications, Services & Experiment Catalogue, Service LCM, Experiment LCM, Multi-site inventory) has an access control client that interacts with Keycloak to validate the access token,

¹⁴ <https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G Platform/experiment-lcm/-/blob/main/API/experiment-lcm.yaml>

export roles, and enforce authorization. This ensures that only authorized users can access the backend resources based on RBAC Access control.

Once authorization is granted or denied, the Portal Web GUI is updated to reflect the status of the access request. The entire process is designed to ensure that only authorized users have access to the resources they need while maintaining the security of the system.

Figure 37: The Software Architecture Process of VITAL-5G Components with Keycloak Integration.

4.2.7.3 APIs and Interfaces

As described at D.2.3 [5], Keycloak, the open-source identity and access management solution, does not offer a specific Interface or API for integration with other applications. Rather, it functions as a standalone, self-contained module that provides secure authentication and authorization services via the OAuth2 protocol.

4.2.7.4 Software Assets

Keycloak is released under the Apache 2.0 license, which is a permissive open-source license that allows users to freely use, modify, and distribute the software for any purpose, including commercial use. As an open-source project, the source code for Keycloak is freely available and can be accessed via the project's GitLab repository¹⁵.

¹⁵ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/access-control

The install folder in the module repository contains the installation instructions and docker files which allow to build and execute this module using Docker.

4.2.8 Slice Manager and Inventory

As already reported in D2.3 [5], the Slice Manager and Inventory component is a management backend software component that is responsible for storing the 5G slices available on each testbed, selection and -if supported- dynamic provisioning and management of 5G slices.

4.2.8.1 Final Release Features

The component's features include:

- Dynamic retrieval of 5G slice information from each of the three 5G testbeds, and storing that information so it could be used for slice decision-making;
- Dynamic provisioning and management of 5G slices and attachment of UEs depending on the testbed capabilities;
- Selection of the 5G slice given the vertical service requirements, based on the decision-making algorithm that is taking into account the retrieved slice information.
- **[NEW]** In D2.3 [5], the overall design has been already described and as such, it has been complemented with the deployment of the slice selection algorithm that is consuming the slice parameters reported by 5G testbeds, and making decisions on the slice selection for the vertical service deployment.

4.2.8.2 Software Architecture

Figure 38 is showing the main software components of the Slice Manager and Inventory component, as well as its interaction with the VITAL-5G testbeds, i.e., their local slice plugins. In particular, Slice Manager is handling the real-time slice information retrieval from the slice plugins, including the possibility to dynamically reconfigure the slices (if available on the testbed). The **Slice Storage** component is storing all the information related to slice profiles, which is further used by **Slice Manager** (offering management and orchestration functionalities) to make decisions on dynamic slice reconfiguration or dynamic UE attachment. In particular, the stored information includes the lists of available slices per testbed, their profile characteristics, and subscribers attached to a particular slice (if available on the testbed).

Figure 38: Software architecture of the Slice Manager and Inventory component.

More details are presented in D2.3 [5].

4.2.8.3 APIs and Interfaces

The complexity of the backend components of the VITAL-5G platform such as Slice Manager and inventory is hidden from the 3rd party experimenters. Nevertheless, the same mechanisms and features will be fully available in terms of managing the slice lifecycle for 3rd party vertical services and Network Applications, in the same way as they are handled for the VITAL-5G internal ones.

4.2.8.4 Software Assets

Although the VITAL-5G Slice Manager and Inventory component is not open source, the interfacing and integration are possible and facilitated by using a REST-based communication mechanism. In particular, in the case of interactions between the Slice Manager and Inventory and Slice Plugins on each of the testbeds, a REST-based communication is used. For more details, see D2.3 [5].

4.2.9 Multi-site Inventory

As described in D2.1 [3], this module acts as centralized repository of information of the VITAL-5G sites information and interfaces with other platform components the query the inventory in question.

4.2.9.1 Final Release Features

This module has been almost entirely released as part of the first-full release version (described in D2.3 [5]). Its features are presented below:

- The multi-site inventory stores records for each site: (i) Devices available (i.e., IoT sensors, gateways, etc); (ii) NFVO credentials and endpoints; (iii) 5G Slicing capabilities, endpoints and available SIMs; (iv) Endpoints for the site monitoring agents.

- It exposes a REST interface which is used by the other platform modules to query the inventory catalogue.
- **[MINOR UPDATE]** In this last release only minor updates to the information models of the records associated with the sites have been introduced, as outcome of the internal integration activities (mainly on the 5G slicing records, to allow specifying the sites' available SIMs).

4.2.9.2 Software Architecture

The internal software architecture of this module is depicted in Figure 39. The functionality implemented by each internal sub-module, based on the description in D2.3 [5], is as follows:

- **REST Controller:** Provides the REST server endpoints, through which site administrators can manage the site information (i.e., managing the devices available, NFVO credentials and 5G Slicing information of each site). Other platform components (e.g., *Service LCM*, *Monitoring Platform*, etc) leverage this REST server to query and retrieve site information. This module is responsible for enforcing the access control mechanisms through the access control client, and initial validation of all the incoming requests. The source code of this component is located in the *it.nextworks.inventory.nbi* package inside the multi-site-inventory project.
- **Inventory Service:** Performs in-depth validation of the creation, deletion, and querying requests, and interacts with the JPA-based repositories to perform the database operations related to the incoming request. The source code for this module is located in the *it.nextworks.inventory.services* of the multi-site-inventory project.
- **JPA-based repositories:** Mediate between the database and the internal modules, hiding the database management and querying complexity. The source code for this module is located in the *it.nextworks.inventory.repos* of the multi-site-inventory project.

Figure 39: Multi-site inventory internal software architecture.

4.2.9.3 APIs and Interfaces

The API definition for this module has been documented in D2.1 [3] and D2.3 [5] and is available in OpenAPI format¹⁶.

4.2.9.4 Software Assets

This module is released under an Apache 2 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository¹⁷.

4.2.10 Monitoring Platform

As reported in D2.3 [5], the VITAL-5G Centralized Monitoring Platform is responsible for: i) collecting different types of metrics/KPIs coming from the three 5G testbed, and ii) sharing collected metrics to the other VITAL-5G platform components (e.g., AI-based diagnostics, or Result-based analytics). The main objective of such a centralized monitoring platform is to facilitate the execution and monitoring of the ongoing experiments, as it enables diagnostic elements to detect anomalies and changes in service and network quality, and to correspondingly act upon those detected events.

4.2.10.1 Final Release Features

The following core features of the Monitoring Platform are in detail described in D2.3 [5]. Minor updates have been made in the Centralized Monitoring Platform based on the learnings from the platform integration phase. These updates refer to the improvements in the data representation on the Grafana panels, with the granularity to VM view for infrastructure metrics, and to Slice ID for network metrics. The complete list of final features is provided as follows:

Dynamic creation of monitoring topics.

- Real-time collection of metrics from the 5G testbeds.
- Dynamic exposure of collected metrics towards external entities.
- Dynamic visualization of the collected metrics
- Dynamic termination of data collection process.
- **[MINOR UPDATE]** Dynamic creation of monitoring topics: The only change compared to D2.3 is that now topic names include the VM reference for the service, platform and infrastructure metrics and with the slice id for network metrics.
- **[MINOR UPDATE]** Real-time collection of metrics from the 5G testbed: the only change compared to D2.3 is that in the JSON payload of what the local testbeds publish towards the VITAL-5G centralized monitoring system all values are now strings.

4.2.10.2 Software Architecture

Figure 40 shows the main software components of the Centralized Monitoring Platform, such as Data Collection Manager and Data Storage Manager, which are responsible for real-time collection of metrics from the VITAL-5G testbeds, and for their efficient storing, respectively. In addition, Figure 40 also shows the interaction between the Centralized Monitoring Platform with the VITAL-5G testbeds (for the purpose of collecting metrics), and with VITAL-5G platform components such as Service LCM (creation of topics when executing experiments), AI-based diagnostics and Result Analytics (dynamic retrieval of metrics), and finally, VITAL-5G Web GUI (displaying collected metrics from different VITAL-5G testbeds).

¹⁶ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/experiment-lcm/-/blob/main/API/experiment-lcm.yaml

¹⁷ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/multi-site-inventory/-/blob/main/API/openapi.json

Figure 40: Software architecture of the Centralized Monitoring Platform.

4.2.10.3 APIs and Interfaces

The complexity of the backend components of the VITAL-5G platform such as Centralized Monitoring Platform is hidden from the 3rd party experimenters. Nevertheless, the same mechanisms and features will be fully available in terms of monitoring network, service, and infrastructure performance, for 3rd party experiments as for the VITAL-5G internal ones.

4.2.10.4 Software Assets

The VITAL-5G Centralized Monitoring Platform is not open source, but the interfacing and integration with this component are facilitated through the use of a ZeroMQ pub/sub mechanism. The examples of Publisher/Subscriber agents are available, and as such, could be also shared with the 3rd party experimenters, see D2.3 [5]. The installation and deployment instructions are provided on the Gitlab repository¹⁸.

4.2.11 Results Analytics

As described in D2.3 [5], the Results Analytics component is responsible for consuming the information generated during a service's operation, analysing it, producing KPIs and providing insights regarding the observed performance and the validation of the requested conditions or SLAs. Additionally, it is capable of generating validation-based triggers to the Closed-loop control process for resizing/scaling network slices and services. Apart from its functional role, this component is also responsible for configuring and controlling the AI-based Diagnostics component, since its operation happens in parallel to the analysis and validation. The configuration information of the AI-based Diagnostics module is similar to the one used by Results Analytics but includes additional context regarding the Network Application, that is tested during the experiment, based on the initial

¹⁸ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/monitoring-platform

configuration received by the LCM component. This additional context includes Network Service identifiers used to retrieve topology information for the elements taking part in the experiment. Information regarding the infrastructure and network resources used to deploy the Network Applications may also be included.

4.2.11.1 Final Release Features

This component has been released in its final form as part of the first-full release version (described in D2.3 [5]). The implemented features of this final release are listed below along with the final updates to the component:

- Metric collection and statistical analysis: the component is responsible to ingest the generated metrics collected, through the monitoring platform, and perform statistical analysis on them in order to provide a more detailed view of the achieved performance.
- KPI calculation and publishing: the component is also responsible to calculate simple or complex KPIs based on the provided formulas and make them available to the monitoring platform for further analysis.
- KPI validation: the validation of the calculated KPIs based on the pre-defined restrictions or SLAs is also supported.
- Report generation: finally, a report is generated containing all the information collected, calculated, and generated in a concise way in order to inform the experiment requester of the achieved performance and results.
- **[MINOR UPDATE]** In this last release only minor bug fixes and updates to the information models have been performed, as the result of the internal integration activities and specifically the Monitoring Platform.

4.2.11.2 Software Architecture

The Result Analysis component is developed using Go, and as shown in Figure 41, it comprises of several submodules and external services, the descriptions of which are as follows:

- Management API: implements the REST server that is responsible for the LCM management of the component, the registration of new services to be monitored and the exposure of the generated results.
- Result Analysis & Validation Engine: handles the statistical analysis of the ingested metrics and the validation of the generated KPIs based on the provided conditions/SLAs.
- KPI Generation Engine: implements the logic behind the calculation of the requested KPIs based on the provided formulas and the metrics used as inputs.
- Management Database: acts as the state manager of the various services that are registered for monitoring on this component and is one of the sources of data that will be included in the report.
- Metric Database: acts as the collected metric storage to be used in the KPI calculation as well as the actual generated KPIs and is one of the sources of data that will be included in the report.
- Report Generator: handle the generation and exposure of the final report.

Figure 41: Result Analysis component internal software architecture.

4.2.11.3 APIs and Interfaces

The API for this module has been documented in D2.3 [5] and is available in OpenAPI format. This API is used by the other modules internally on a platform level and is not exposed to external users (3rd parties). The generated output from this component can be retrieved from the Monitoring platform, for the KPIs, and the Portal (report).

4.2.11.4 Software Assets

This module is proprietary, and as such is released in binary format, which is available in the project's Gitlab repository.

4.2.12 AI-based Diagnostics

As described in D2.3 [5], the AI-based Diagnostics component consumes information regarding to a service's performance, during an experiment, and after analysing that information, produces insights on the observed performance of the various elements that comprise the service. In order to perform the required operations, the diagnostic process utilizes as input the generated metrics and KPIs collected from the execution of similar experiments of the same service, along with the service topology and resources information regarding the specific service. Experiments are considered similar when they include the same metrics and KPIs and as such will generate the same number of features for the AI models. This information is used, at first as the training data set for the AI models generated per Network Application, and afterwards, provided that a sufficient training data set of the models has been achieved, it is used as input data for the inference stage of the same models. The AI-based Diagnostics component is also responsible for detecting anomalies in the behaviour of the various elements as well as identifying possible root causes of detected problems or performance degradations during the experiment. After the detection of such anomalies and performance degradations, it also triggers diagnostic events to the Closed-loop control process in order to suggest the necessary actions to alleviate these issues. To accomplish that, various AI algorithms has been implemented as modules to be used as part of the Anomaly detection and the Root Cause Analysis mechanisms. Such algorithms are Self Organized Maps (SOM) and DBSCAN clustering as well as custom algorithms for topological investigation, correlation, and root cause analysis.

4.2.12.1 Final Release Features

This component has been released in its final form as part of the first-full release version (described in D2.3 [5]). In this last release only minor bug fixes and updates to the information models have been performed, as well as calibration of the AI models generation process, as the result of the internal integration activities and specifically the Monitoring platform.

4.2.12.2 Software Architecture

The AI-based Diagnostics component is developed using Go and Python, for the AI algorithms module, and as shown in Figure 42, it comprises several submodules and external services, the descriptions of which are as follows:

- Management API: implements the REST server that is responsible for the LCM management of the component, the registration of new services to be monitored and the exposure of the diagnosis results.
- Vectorizer: handles the ingestion of the collected metrics and KPIs, their spatiotemporal correlation and their organization into vectors suitable to be consumed by the AI algorithms.
- AI Algorithms module: implements the various AI algorithms used in the diagnostic process for anomaly detection and root cause analysis.
- Management database: acts as the state manager of the various services that are registered for monitoring on this component and is one of the sources of data that will be included in the report.
- Metric database: acts as the storage of the raw and analysed vectors to be used in the diagnostic process and is one of the sources of data that will be included in the report.

Figure 42: AI Diagnostic component internal software architecture.

4.2.12.3 APIs and Interfaces

The API for this module has been documented in D2.3 [5] and is available in OpenAPI format. This API is used by the other modules internally on a platform level and is not exposed to external users (3rd parties). The generated output from this component can be retrieved from the Portal (report).

4.2.12.4 Software Assets

This module is proprietary, and as such is released in binary format, which is available in the project's Gitlab repository.

4.2.13 ML/Analytics Toolkit

This platform component offers AI/ML capabilities for service data post processing, which aims to identify outlying behaviour/abnormal data with respect to monitored KPIs. The functionality was originally developed in the context of VA3 Network Application [3][5], however it was decided to be integrated with the VITAL-5G Platform in order to complement the existing analytics and AI features and allow for a horizontal to the project impact, as it will allow the user to process the results of the experiments and train their own models and acquire results with zero code.

4.2.13.1 Final Release Features

This final release features include:

- ML-based approaches for following two density-based clustering approaches are offered:
 - Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN)
 - Ordering Points To Identify the Clustering Structure (OPTICS)

Their purpose is to detect dense areas where data form clusters, while at the same time data points in sparse areas are considered outliers.

- In addition to the above, One Class Support Vector Machine (SVM) is used also as an unsupervised model that learns the boundaries for the normal data points and therefore any points outside these boundaries are considered as outliers/anomalies.
- The implementation is based on the Scikit-learn library [10]. The solution allows for Bayesian hyperparameter optimization, selecting the best hyperparameters for each model and logs all training metrics and artifacts to MLflow [11].
- Model autotune engine that allows for Bayesian hyperparameter optimization, selecting the best hyperparameters for each model and logs all training metrics and artifacts to MLflow.
- User interface functionalities (part of Portal Web GUI) that support model configuration and training, as well as exploration of post-processing results (see Figure 43).
- An MLflow-specific view allows users monitor the various ML results and compare their performance.
- **[NEW]** Added PostgreSQL [12] connector to monitoring components database.
- **[NEW/UPDATED]** Use of PostgreSQL and MinIO [8] for storage of model artifacts and results.
- **[DEPRECATED]** Due to the integration to the platform, features related to Influx database connector and ingestion to a Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) [13] were deprecated.

Figure 43: ML/Analytics Toolkit views.

4.2.13.2 Software Architecture

Figure 44: ML/Analytics Toolkit software architecture.

As shown in Figure 44, the ML/Analytics Toolkit acquires data persisted in the monitoring component of the VITAL-5G Platform, the ML engine allows for the training and deployment of the ML models, focusing is on the outlier/anomaly detection approaches. The autotune engine allows for Bayesian hyperparameter optimization, selecting the best hyperparameters for each model and logs all training metrics and artifacts to MLflow.

4.2.13.3 APIs and Interfaces

As part of the Platform components all APIs are internal to the Platform.

4.2.13.4 Software Assets

This software is proprietary. However, Platform users in the context of VITAL-5G will be given the opportunity to run various ML-models, acquire results, as well as details on model type, hyperparameters and model performance through the Portal Web GUI.

4.2.14 Intent-based Requests Manager

The Intent-based Requests Manager provides an alternative mechanism to define VITAL-5G experiments, adopting an approach based on the natural language.

4.2.14.1 Final Release Features

The module supports two mechanisms that helps the experimenters to express their intentions. One is based on free text, where experimenters can write a sentence to describe the characteristics of the desired experiment. The description is then automatically translated by the module into a blueprint. The second mechanism is based on guided selection and filling of the fields that defines an experiment, through a set of web pages that guides the experimenter during the entire procedure.

The Intent-based Requests Manager is based on the 5G-EVE intent-based tool, but with several major enhancements. In particular, the following have been performed so that the module may work with VITAL-5G models and interact with other VITAL-5G modules:

- **[NEW]** Most of the intent-based tool internal workings have been reused, but they have been adapted to the use cases and models (blueprints, descriptors, etc.) developed in VITAL-5G.
- **[NEW]** The Intent-based tool GUI has been redesigned and adapted for the VITAL-5G use cases, domains as well as visual identity.
- **[NEW]** Interaction between the experiment LCM and the intent-based manager is enabled such that it can trigger experiments in the facility where the Network Applications are deployed/onboarded.
- **[NEW]** Access Control integration: Validation of the user roles to access the experiment setup and scheduling. Use case mapping to authorize request.

4.2.14.2 Software Architecture

Figure 45: Intent-based Requests Manager software architecture.

The Intent-based Requests Manager architecture is depicted in Figure 45 and consists of a Translator tool and VS Blueprint creator page. The translator tool takes the information provided either via the experiment description or guided selection page and creates the Vertical Service blueprint. If information is missing, it will open a new webpage where the experimenter can input the missing information.

Before deploying the experiment, it checks the multi-site inventory for the availability of resources. If they are not available, the experimenter is redirected to the GUI for recreating the experiment. If they are available, then the experiment is deployed by calling the experiment LCM component.

4.2.14.3 APIs and Interfaces

A GUI is available for interested parties (experimenters) to define their VITAL-5G experiments (Figure 46).

Figure 46: Intent-based Requests Manager GUI.

4.2.14.4 Software Assets

This module is released with an Apache 2.0 based open-source license, and the code is available in the VITAL-5G software Gitlab repositories¹⁹.

4.3 Automated Closed-loop Workflows and Implementation

One of the key features introduced in this release of the VITAL-5G Platform is the support of automated closed-loop workflows to enable automated lifecycle management actions upon detection of a certain monitoring condition or the firing of a diagnostic event. In Section 4.1 of D2.3 [5], we established the software-oriented workflows, depicted in Figure 47, in order to enable these automated closed-loops, and further generalized at an architectural level in D1.3 [2]. The workflow depicted in the figure, uses the *RuntimeModifications* associated to the Vertical Service, and defined in the VSB. In Section 2.2 we provide the full specification of the VSB data model, which details the modifications of the VSB to enable the definition of the *RuntimeModifications*. We also refer to Section 2.2 for further details regarding the types of triggers and the types of actions. As detailed in the figure, the *Service LCM*, uses the *RuntimeModifications* to internally configure the events/metrics to monitor, and subscribing to the correspondent topics through the API of the *Service & Network Monitoring* described in Section 4.2.8.

¹⁹ https://gitlab.slicenet.oteresearch.gr/vital-5g_platform/ibn-manager

Figure 47: Service instantiation and execution for closed-control loop support.

In Figure 48 we provide an example of the message generated by the *AI-based diagnostics* module to signal the occurrence of a certain event and pushed into the diagnostic topic in the *Monitoring Platform (Centralized)*.

```

{
  "id": "4d782dfe-625d-4582-b877-1d08404b09e3",
  "vmId": "7e24e6ea-bddf-4f3c-abe2-f07200e8d4b2",
  "networkSliceId": "8570fa6b-7981-4065-817a-0a69b28c9c47",
  "typeServiceId": "7468d476-e06c-4a87-adc2-723a2fd64325",
  "service": "7d11a38a-9cd7-4d1a-bae1-8d97197206b8",
  "timestamp": 1666277068.12312312,
  "type": "diagnostic",
  "context": {
    "category": "5G_SLICE_UNDERPERFORMANCE"
  }
}
    
```

Figure 48: AI-Diagnostic event message.

The *Service LCM* upon detecting the triggering condition, internally triggers the execution of the established modification: (i) Network Slice modification, to modify the network resources of the 5G slice attached to the service instance; (ii) Network Service scale, to modify the computing resources allocated to the Network Applications. This functionality is also exposed through a REST-based interface, to enable external modules or

technicians to trigger the modification on demand. The API to trigger is available in OpenAPI format as described in Section 4.2.3.3.

In the case of Network service scaling, the *Service LCM* uses OSM primitives to trigger the scaling procedure, as depicted in Figure 49. In the case of Network Slice modification, the *Service LCM* uses the API exposed the *Multi-site 5G Slice Manager and Inventory*. Depending on the testbed capabilities, the network slice modification is performed by either creating/deploying a new slice or reconfiguring the existing one, thereby enabling the fulfilment of requirements of vertical services that are associated with the slices. The 5G Slice Manager and Inventory component is in charge of processing this modification request, which is further sending corresponding requests to slice plugins installed on the VITAL-5G testbeds. For instance, the Galati/ Bucharest VITAL-5G testbed already supports a certain level of dynamic slice modification. Thus, once the slice plugin receives the modification request from the Slice Manager and Inventory component, it is capable of creating a new instance with the newly defined parameters, terminating the old slice that did not perform as expected. On the other hand, the other two testbeds (Antwerp and Athens) support the dynamic user attachment to the slice and the dynamic retrieval of slice features, but the modification of the slices' during runtime is not fully supported on the 5G Core level. Thus, the requests for slice modification are received at the slice plugin level on the testbed, but processing of such request on the Core level is not supported. In the case of Antwerp testbed, the creation/termination of new/old slices is currently being deployed through interfacing with Telenet Core API gateway, which allows slice plugins developed by IMEC to retrieve slice features and performance, and to request creation of new slices depending on the decision made during the closed-loop procedures on the VITAL-5G platform level. The outcomes of the aforementioned activities will be presented as part of the trialing activities in subsequent WP4 deliverables.

Figure 49: Network Service Scaling and 5G slice Modification workflows.

5 Final Version of the VITAL-5G Network Applications

5.1 Network Applications & Evolution

Section 5 of the deliverable presents the consortium's implemented Network Applications. As was the case for the VITAL-5G Platform components, each Network Application is either completely new and developed within the VITAL-5G project or reused based on previous projects and evolved during the project's lifetime. Furthermore, minor, major and/or final releases have been described in previous deliverables. The following table (Table 5) lists the Network Application per Use Case (UC), clarifies which are new, have been updated/improved within the project, and how they compare with their last version/release.

Table 4: Network Application updates compared to (a) previous projects and (b) previous version/release.

UC	Network Application	Justification (New/Reused)	Updates since last deliverable/release?
UC1	Assisted vessel navigation (VS6)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	(i) Addition of the module for automatic static map generation. (ii) Update of the communication mechanism to use the Zenoh library [17]. In addition, a switch was added to provide both the old (ZeroMQ [18]-based) and the new (Zenoh-based) communication schemes, to help in trials. The user has the choice to use either of them through configuration settings. (iii) Interface with VS8 based on Zenoh. (iv) Interface with VS5 based on Zenoh.
	Navigation speed optimizer (VS7)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	(i) Change of the communication mechanism with VS8 and VS5 from ZeroMQ to Zenoh
	Monitoring dashboard (VS5)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	(i) Use of Zenoh instead of ZeroMQ for communication with other Network Applications. (ii) Integration with VA5 and VS6. (iii) Visualization improvement.
	Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessels (VS8)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	Update of the communication mechanism to use the Eclipse Zenoh technology for the communication between Network Applications.
	Real time digital twin (VA5)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	(i) Detection of moving obstacles. (ii) Interface with VS5: addition of a zenoh communication interface, for testing purposes only. (iii) Interface with the vessel: addition of a RTSP [19] communication interface upon requirement from SF. (iv) New interface with VS8 upon requirement from SF. (v) New data collection module to collect radar data from the boat used for trialing and demonstration.
UC2	Data stream organization (VA6)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	No updates since D2.3.

	Onboard data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel (VS9)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	Reorganization of MQTT topic names Support for GPS data
	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing (VA2)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project, based also on Incelligent proprietary work for ML components	Updated data schema to fit UC2 sensor setup since last release in D2.3. Also, from the previous release the sensors specific ingestion data functionalities moved to VA6, so as not to overlap, and only the data manipulation and ML functionalities remained.
	Remote inspection & risk assessment (VA3)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project, based also on Incelligent proprietary work for ML components	Deprecated and included as platform functionality. Previous version in D2.3
UC3	Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning (VS1)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Updated Logistics Lifecycle Management Service (Logistics LCM), an API providing access to pending transportation jobs and warehouse products. (ii) Deployed a telemetry station hosting a warehouse simulator which interacts with the VS1 Network application to simulate workers fulfilling orders in a warehouse. The simulated data are published over the deployed 5G network and runs 24/7 which allows the collection of metrics for evaluation and optimization. Additionally, the telemetry station includes a camera sending video to the Video service exposed by the VS2 network application. This has been used to further stress the 5G network and collect metrics for video bitrate and latency.
	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation (VA1)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	WINGSChariot frontend: The user interface enables the building of configurable dashboards with custom layouts to achieve the required workflows. Widgets include streaming video players, virtual joysticks for remote control, a digital twin (floorplan) for the warehouse, external maps, sensor state cards and tables for listing T&L jobs and products.
	Human-robot collaboration (VS2)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	(i) Computational offloading updates: The core of the follow-me functionality is based on the Terabee™ ultrawide band positioning system. However, the computational offloading module can help to increase the accuracy of this operation by making available a more sophisticated positioning system. This includes a “Leg Detector” module which provides an estimate for the position of a human in front of an AGV using Lidar data and improves the localization accuracy compared

			<p>to when using only the Terabee™ positioning system.</p> <p>(ii) Video controller and streaming server updates, assisting a human operator for remote control of the AGV. The video service has been integrated with VA1 and video players have been exposed to the WINGSChariot web interface for monitoring and remote control of the AGV. The Video service now includes a measurement of the video latency through a custom implementation which passes timestamps along with the video frames.</p>
Cross-UC	IoT Management platform for (i) unified collection, storage and basic processing of IoT data and (ii) control of actuators, interacting with multiple types of field buses (VA4)	Network Application based on the re-packaging and adaptation of existing commercial solutions based on proprietary software	Fully released in D2.3
	AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance (VS3)	Network Application based on the re-packaging and adaptation of existing commercial solutions based on proprietary software	Fully released in D2.4
	Technical data visualization (VS4)	Network Application based on the re-packaging and adaptation of existing commercial solutions based on proprietary software	Fully released in D2.4

Similarly, the following table describes the access type for 3rd parties and links to repositories.

Table 5: Network Applications’ access for 3rd parties and links to repositories.

UC	Network Application	Access for the 3rd-party experimenters (PRIVATE, PUBLIC, RESTRICTED)	Type of access for the 3rd-party experimenters.	Links to repositories
UC1	Assisted vessel navigation (VS6)	RESTRICTED	Access to planned waypoints (output of the Network Application).	N/A
	Navigation speed optimizer (VS7)	PUBLIC	Available on the platform catalogue for use, and also released as open source for reference to 3rd party experimenters.	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vs7

	Monitoring dashboard (VS5)	RESTRICTED	Access to the python code and JavaScript for the front end	N/A
	Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessels (VS8)	RESTRICTED	Access to GNSS data	N/A
	Real time digital twin (VA5)	RESTRICTED	Access to obstacle map and boundaries of moving objects (output of the Network Application).	N/A
UC2	Data stream organization (VA6)	PUBLIC	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed	https://gitlab.slicenet.oterese.arch.gr/vital-5g-netapps/data-stream-organization
	Onboard data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel (VS9)	PUBLIC	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed	https://gitlab.slicenet.oterese.arch.gr/vital-5g-netapps/data-collection-navrom
	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing (VA2)	RESTRICTED	Through the UI and APIs to 3rd parties: access to ML results in Map view; allow for running various ML-models, acquiring results as well as details on model type, hyperparameters and model performance during the training stage.	N/A
	Remote inspection & risk assessment (VA3)	N/A,as component was deprecated.	NA	N/A
UC3	Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning (VS1)	RESTRICTED	Access to sensor data; Access to warehouse simulator data	Virtual Machine image at https://share.wings-ict-solutions.dev/vital5g/ (Proprietary License)
	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation (VA1)	RESTRICTED	Access to sensor data	Virtual Machine image at https://share.wings-ict-solutions.dev/vital5g/ (Proprietary License)
	Human-robot collaboration (VS2)	RESTRICTED	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed	Virtual Machine image at https://share.wings-ict-solutions.dev/vital5g/ (Proprietary License)

Cross-UC	IoT Management platform for (i) unified collection, storage and basic processing of IoT data and (ii) control of actuators, interacting with multiple types of field buses (VA4)	RESTRICTED	Usage of this Network Application may be granted to 3rd parties after negotiation.	Available as a set of VM snapshots (qcow2 format) through the following FTP: Server: mercurio.nextworks.it Port: 9292
	AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance (VS3)	RESTRICTED	Usage of this Network Application may be granted to 3rd parties after negotiation.	Available as a set of VM snapshots (qcow2 format) through the following FTP: Server: mercurio.nextworks.it Port: 9292
	Technical data visualization (VS4)	RESTRICTED	Usage of this Network Application may be granted to 3rd parties after negotiation.	Available as a set of VM snapshots (qcow2 format) through the following FTP: Server: mercurio.nextworks.it Port: 9292

5.2 VA1 Distributed Sensor Data Ingestion, Fusion & Automation

The VA1 Network Application titled “Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation” is responsible for the data ingestion and two-way communication with on-site equipment, the automation of tasks and transformations based on a rule engine, as well as the monitoring of the solution. The components and architecture of the Network Application have been described in deliverable D2.1 [3].

5.2.1 Final Release Features

Unlike the early drop of VA1 (as documented at D2.2 [4]) which was only tested using simulators, the final version has been also integrated with the VS1 and VS2 Network Applications and has been tested with physical IoT devices and a Clearpath Boxer 2.4 AGV for the verification of its functional operation.

- **[NEW] WINGSChariot frontend:** The user interface enables the building of configurable dashboards with custom layouts to achieve the required workflows. Widgets include streaming video players, virtual joysticks for remote control, a digital twin (floorplan) for the warehouse, external maps, sensor state cards and tables for listing T&L jobs and products.
- **Core IoT Controller:** It is the main application logic layer which combines data (events and states), and services to facilitate the two-way interaction with the monitored and controlled IoT devices. It connects and synchronizes the whole Network Application infrastructure and services by the means of a common event loop and state machine.
- **MQTT/HTTP:** For enabling the communication between off-site and on-site infrastructure. Raw data from on-site equipment and environmental sensors are collected in real time through the MQTT and REST API endpoints. Two-way communication is achieved by providing feedback and control commands to the on-site equipment through the same protocols.
- **Reasoning engine:** It includes an automation rules engine and transformation services to provide decision support.
- **Persistence engine:** It provides persistence and caching services to all other Network Application components. The final version includes persistence of IoT states and operational data (orders, packages) for logistics operations.

Figure 50: WINGSChariot screenshot of 3D Floorplan view.

Figure 51: WINGSChariot screenshot - Charts and Sensor Cards.

5.2.2 Software Architecture

Figure 52: VA1 Components.

Figure 52 presents the VA1 components. The Core IoT Controller synchronizes the whole Network Application infrastructure and services by means of a common event loop and state machine. State changes are persisted to a PostgreSQL database. The rules engine operates either on a scheduled or event-based basis. Input and output are supported by the MQTT and HTTP interfaces which are described in the following section.

5.2.3 APIs and Interfaces

The MQTT and HTTP interfaces are exposed and made available through the 5G network for two-way communication with onsite equipment.

- MQTT interface: The interface is used for two-way communication with onsite equipment such as AGVs and IoT devices. The MQTT interface is also used by other Network applications such as VS2 for receiving raw data and sending optimized results for field assistance.
- HTTP interface: The HTTP interface is mainly used for accessing persisted data. It can also be used by privileged accounts for administration tasks.

The MQTT and non-privileged HTTP interfaces can be accessed by third parties although it would be easier to interact with the platform by using the configurable and flexible WINGSChariot interface which does not require coding.

5.2.4 Deployment

The components of VA1 are provided as a Virtual Machine image instantiated in the Athens testbed. It is important to note that the same Network Application can be deployed in other trial sites, i.e., VITAL-5G testbeds.

5.2.5 Software assets

The VA1 Network Application includes open-source and closed-source components. The closed-source components are covered by a proprietary license (provided by WINGS ICT Solutions) which allows the usage of the Network Applications within the scope of VITAL-5G, both by the VITAL-5G partners and third-party experimenters.

The VA1 Network Application is offered as Virtual Machine image at <https://share.wings-ict-solutions.dev/vital5g/>. Software keys and guidance are provided to partners for onboarding the VM in the VITAL-5G platform. The VM has been deployed on the Athens testbed.

5.3 VA2 Distributed Sensor Data Ingestion, Fusion & Post-processing

This Network Application focuses on functionalities related to data manipulation, fusion and persistence and the supervised machine learning (ML)-related functionalities (see also Deliverable 2.3 [5]). Lastly, a dedicated user interface (UI) is included so as to allow users to use VA2 and visualize results easily.

5.3.1 Final Release Features

More specifically, the main functionalities supported are:

- **[UPDATED]** Data Collection: Responsible for the collection of data through the southbound interfacing with the testbed(s) and/or external sources and Network Applications. This functionality was updated to fit the updated use case sensor set up.
- Data Fusion: Performs the logical transformation of data to be further utilized. It allows for the spatiotemporal correlation of the received information and applies transformations and manipulations necessary.
- ML module: It is comprised of ML engine, the Autotune Engine, and the ML Registry. It incorporates mechanisms that ensure the optimal ML model will be used for advanced analytics depending on the application. In this case, the forecasting/ supervising approaches are explored as they are more relevant to VA2 Network Application-related applications. The ML algorithms considered are (a) Seasonal Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average with eXogenous factors (SARIMAX) model using the Statsmodels library [15], and (b) Prophet [16], an automatic forecasting procedure for time series data based on an additive model where non-linear trends are fit with seasonality and other effects (e.g. holidays).
- Data Persistence: This component refers to a distributed data lake allowing for storage of both structured and unstructured data. It is where the raw data/KPIs, as well as their transformations and the ML modelling results are persisted.

Based on the aforementioned functionalities, VA2's software architecture is presented in Figure 54.

Indicative views of the Network Application's user interface are presented in Figure 53.

Figure 53: VA2 indicative user interface views.

5.3.2 Software Architecture

A description of the various functional blocks of VA2 was provided in D2.1 [3] and further specified in D2.3 [5]. In short, sensor data are ingested through the appropriate interfaces (Influx-Hive connector) and stored. Apache Airflow [14] assists in the data operations pipelines to allow for the data pipelines before ML models can be employed. The Autotune Engine allows for an automated selection of the best ML model through a hyperparameter tuning process, while all training metrics and model artifacts are logged in MLflow [11]. It should be noted that although not originally included in the Network Application architecture and was not part of VA2, a UI/dashboard has also been developed as an added component that can exploit the VA2 mechanisms and visualize results. It presents vessel trajectory-related results, but also includes a form where 3rd party users can train their own models by choosing from the models and respective hyperparameters available and specifying the ingested data used for model development. At the same time, they can also monitor, through an MLflow-specific view, the various ML results and compare their performance.

Figure 54: VA2 software architecture.

5.3.3 APIs and Interfaces

A detailed description for the APIs developed based on (and fully compatible with) the OpenAPI specification has been provided in D2.3 [5]. These APIs are split as: (a) public, i.e. available to 3rd parties; and (b) private, meaning that the relevant APIs are indirectly accessible to 3rd parties only through the Network Application UI.

5.3.4 Deployment

While for the case of forecasting future trajectories the selected data used are the vessel's position, have changed to GPS sensor data (previously utilizing AIS data, see section 5.17), this Network Application also allows for data fusion of information coming from different sensors to be persisted in Apache HDFS and further utilized either by the Network Application's generic forecasting models or by other Network Applications/ 3rd parties.

5.3.5 Software assets

The early drop release was under an AGPLv3 licence. However, the current ML-related and data fusion scheme work is proprietary, and the relevant components will be provided as Docker images.

Through the delivered UI and APIs to 3rd parties, users will be given the opportunity to run various ML-models, acquiring results as well as details on model type, hyperparameters and model performance during the training stage.

5.4 VA3 Predictive Maintenance

The functionality of this Network Application has been shifted and incorporated as a platform level component, in order to: (i) enrich the AI/ML-based reporting capabilities of the VITAL-5G platform: (ii) Benefit from the functionality provided by the services of this Network Application in a wider set of scenarios (see Section 4.2.13).

5.5 VA4 IoT Management Platform

5.5.1 Final Release Features

The IoT Management Platform developed by NXW, as described in D2.1 [3], is a Network Application for the collection of technical monitoring data (e.g., environmental data, engines operational data, technical systems operational data) from heterogeneous systems available in the building (for warehouse) or on-board (for vessel). In VITAL-5G we use this Network Application to collect IoT sensor data from the warehouse infrastructure of the Greek testbed. This information is exposed through different interfaces to other Network Applications (e.g. VS3 and VS4), in order to provide advanced service oriented functionality. This Network application was completely released in the first-full-release described in D2.3 [5].

5.5.2 Software Architecture

Figure 55: VA4 Internal functional blocks.

In Figure 55 we depict the internal software architecture of this Network Application, as originally depicted in D2.3 [5].

- **REST Controller:** This component exposes a REST Interface to enable the configuration and management of the other functional blocks of the Network Application: (i) Management and retrieval of data sources (through the configuration of IoT Monitored objects, or buses); (ii) Configuration and management of the Datastore Backend for persistency and historical data retrieval of monitored data; (iii) Definition and visualization of alarms and events based on thresholds or custom triggers.
- **IoT Supervisor:** This module interacts with the data sources to retrieve the data, providing a layer of abstraction through a unified interface. The data is retrieved through the data injection interface of the module, and exposed to the rest of the modules through the Message Broker.
- **Message Broker:** This module leverages RabbitMQ to implement the logic to distribute messages with the streams of IoT monitored data. In this sense, the IoT Supervisor module injects the data on the Message Broker, which is then used by the other modules through a subscription-based mechanism.

- **Datastore and Dashboard:** This module implements the scalable and flexible logic to store and visualize timeseries based data. This is used to store the monitoring information coming from the IoT devices.
- **IoT event & alarm Manager:** Implements the logic for the management, triggering and visualization of IoT Events and Alarms based on custom complex conditions, which may be based on static or dynamic data coming from one or more sensors. The events and alarm can trigger REST based request towards external modules, or push messages into the message broker.

5.5.3 APIs and Interfaces

The API exposed by the REST controller to enable the configuration of data sources, management and retrieval of IoT events and alerts, and retrieval of monitored data is available in OpenAPI format in the project Gitlab Repository.

5.5.4 Deployment

In Figure 56 we depicted the deployment scenarios defined in D2.3 [5]. As detailed in the picture there are two model scenarios for the deployment of this Network Application. In the first scenario, the one targeted in the VITAL-5G internal trials, VA4 leverages another Network Application (VA1) as data source for IoT Monitored information. This scenario is useful when the provider of the IoT devices and infrastructure wants to enforce a tight control on the access to the IoT infrastructure and monitoring information (and avoid direct exposure). In this scenario VA1 is attached to the 5G network to interface with the IoT devices on the field. In the second scenario VA4 is directly attached to the 5G network and directly connected to the IoT devices in the field, using a URLLC based slice.

Figure 56: VA4 Deployment Scenarios.

5.5.5 Software assets

As detailed in D2.3 [5], VA4 is made available as a set of VM snapshots (qcow2 format) through the following FTP:

Server: mercurio.nextworks.it

Port: 9292

Files:

- **Rest Controller:** Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2
- **IoT Supervisor:** Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2
- **Message Broker:** Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2
- **IoT alarm & event manager:** Vital5G_VA4_Rest_Controller.qcow2
- **Datastore & Dashboard:** Vital5G_VA4_Datastore_Dashboard.qcow2

5.6 VA5 Real Time Digital Twin

The responsibility of this Network Application is to perform situational awareness. It makes use of all available radar sensor data to build a real-time obstacle map of the surroundings of the vessel in the Port of Antwerp and to identify the moving objects.

5.6.1 Final Release Features

The final release features include:

- Pre-processing of radar images using image processing techniques to reduce the noise of radar images and prepare the data for further processing.
- **[NEW]** The moving objects detection is a new feature which was added since the last release. This feature allows to estimate a distinction between static obstacles and moving obstacles, in an attempt to provide the captain with a focus on moving objects. This feature relies in particular on background subtraction, contour detection, and retrieval of waterway area information, which were developed for that purpose.
- **[NEW]** A new communication mechanism was also added in this release, using the Zenoh library [17], as an alternative to the previous ZeroMQ [18] mechanism. In addition, due to a requirement from SF to use RTSP [19] to receive radar data from the vessel, such a mechanism was also added.
- **[NEW]** A new module was added which allows to collect vessel data (latitude, longitude, heading) and radar images received in real-time. The purpose of this module was to collect radar images that had the same format as the one provided by the equipment used for trials and demonstration purposes. It is however not part of the process and initial aim of the VA5 Network Application and is therefore not mentioned in the next sections.

5.6.2 Software Architecture

To create a digital twin of the environment, on-board sensor data is required. This data is received directly from the vessel via a 5G interface. VA5 contains the following functional blocks:

- **Background Subtraction:** This module performs a first set of image processing operations which reduce the noise of radar images and limits the detection of spurious obstacles.
- **Contour Detection:** This module performs further noise reduction and determines the bounding boxes of the detected obstacles.
- **Occupancy Map Creation:** This module generates the binary occupancy map and necessary metadata which will serve as input to the path planning Network Application VS6.

- **Moving Objects Detection:** This module generates the list of bounding boxes around moving objects, which will be sent to the monitoring dashboard Network Application VS5 to assist the captain.

Figure 57 displays the functional architecture of the VA5 Network Application.

Figure 57: VA5 functional architecture.

Visuals of output examples of VA5 are provided in Figure 58.

Figure 58: VA5 visuals of output examples: Moving object detection (estimated boundaries and headings of moving objects).

5.6.3 APIs and Interfaces

In the final release, VA5 has the following interfaces:

- With the vessel, which sends the necessary radar images and metadata.

- With VS6 (Assisted vessel navigation), which receives a map of the environment and the associated metadata.
- With VS5 (Remote vessel monitoring), which receives a list of bounding boxes of moving objects.

Data exchanges with other Network Applications are ensured by the ZeroMQ or Zenoh library [17][18].

Figure 59 displays the network architecture of the VA5 Network Application.

Figure 59: VA5 network architecture.

5.6.4 Deployment

VA5 is made available as a virtual machine instantiated on IMEC servers in the Antwerp testbed.

5.6.5 Software assets

The access to the Real-time digital twin Network Application is restricted to the output obstacle map and obstacle metadata. VA5 is developed by IMEC, but it relies on the sensors of SF for the Antwerp testbed.

5.7 VA6 Data Stream Organization

As described in D2.1-D2.3 [3][4][5], the main role of VA6 is to organize the data streams that are coming from different sensors or from video streaming (currently available from VS9, but in general available from any other external Network Application or 3rd party) so that they are transmitted over a 5G network and permit the sensing system to be used by specific services and applications.

5.7.1 Final Release Features

The final release of VA6 currently has the following features:

- Supports organization of data according to payload content
- Supports receiving data via Pub/Sub paradigms
- Supports custom processing functions (for organizing stream)

VA6 receives data from other Network Applications or 3rd parties that have data to be sent using the MQTT protocol. Its software architecture is illustrated in Figure 60.

5.7.2 Software Architecture

The main components of VA6 are:

1. An adaptor component from MQTT broker to InfluxDB [20]– a Python script that subscribes to a set of topics defined in the map configuration file and publishes the received data through the carbon²⁰ interface of InfluxDB.

The types of payloads supported, their format and examples are described in detail in D2.3 [5].

2. Time Series Database (OpenSource, InfluxDB) - InfluxDB 1.8 is used where the data is organized in databases and measurements. For VA6 a single database is used. Each measurement presents the data in the associated fields.
3. Visualisation Engine (Grafana [21]) - two types of dashboards for the visualisation engine are used: (a) Graphical representations of time variation of measured parameters (see example in Figure 61); (b) Overlay map displaying time series data.

A detailed description of VA6 can be found in D2.3 [5].

Figure 60: Software architecture of the first release of the VA6 Network Application.

Figure 61: Example visualisation from the Grafana engine.

5.7.3 APIs and Interfaces

VA6 offers:

- An HTTP REST API interface used for querying the InfluxDB and supporting InfluxQL queries. The interface is the standard one offered by InfluxDB, and a full reference is available online.

²⁰ https://docs.influxdata.com/influxdb/v1.8/supported_protocols/graphite/

- A Grafana-based interface using the Worldmap Panel Plugin for Grafana²¹

For 3rd party or external network application use, the most important API endpoint for obtaining information from the InfluxDB is the *query* endpoint. An example usage can be seen in Table 7 .

Table 6: VA6 Example usage of API query endpoint.

Command/response	Example
/query	<pre>curl -G 'http://172.28.22.165:8086/query?db=graphite' - -data-urlencode 'q=SELECT * FROM "mqtt.uc2.real.va6.mercur304.HUM.value"'</pre>
<pre>Accept: */* HTTP/1.1 200 OK Content-Type: application/json</pre>	<pre>{ "results": [{ "statement_id": 0, "series": [{ "name": "mqtt.uc2.real.va6.mercur304.HUM.value", "columns": ["time", "value"], "values": [["2023-04-05T20:41:19Z", 49.339844], ["2023-04-05T20:42:51Z", 49.245117], ... (omitted for brevity) ["2023-04-06T08:41:40Z", 73.257812]] }] }] }</pre>

5.7.4 Deployment

It uses the same sensors as in VS9 as data is received via VS9 (see section 5.17).

²¹ <https://grafana.com/grafana/plugins/grafana-worldmap-panel/>

5.7.5 Software assets

This module is released with an Apache 2.0 based open-source license, and the code is available in the VITAL-5G software Gitlab repositories²².

5.8 VA7 Network Data Collection

Network Data Collection is a new vertical-agnostic Network Application, which is designed and developed for the purpose of making any Network Application network-aware, by informing it about the real-time network performance for a particular type of 5G slice. The level of network-awareness depends on each Network Application and the way it processes the data collected from VA7, and this aspect is out of scope of this Network Application.

In particular, VA7 provides a dynamic mechanism for collecting real-time network data from a particular trial site and 5G testbed by subscribing to specific topics on the local monitoring platform. As the local monitoring system on the Antwerp 5G testbed allows subscribers to subscribe to different topics using ZeroMQ [18] mechanism, VA7 is designed and developed to accommodate that communication principle. Running VA7 on the other testbeds is possible, with further modifications that will allow VA7 to subscribe to the data published by the Centralized Monitoring platform. The data published on the Centralized monitoring platform depends on the trial site, thus, VA7 allows any Network Application to discover all topics that are currently available and contain data that can be pulled (either historical or real-time). The collected data can be used for adjusting the internal work of Network Applications, such as reducing the video resolution, decreasing the frequency of data (sensors, radar), or adjusting internal algorithms to compensate for lower network quality.

5.8.1 Final Release Features

The functional components of VA7 are illustrated in Figure 62, including the internal components such as Network Data Collector, Network Data Processor, and Network Data Publisher, as well as the interaction between the Network Data Collector and Centralized Monitoring Platform. The internal functional components are enabling the following features of Network Data Collection:

- **[NEW]** Dynamic collection of network data: the process of collecting network data is achieved through the pub/sub mechanism, where Network Data Collector collects data from the monitoring platform. This data combines all network metrics that are pushed from the three 5G testbeds.
- **[NEW]** Data processing: This step is important as it is performing the data cleanup and clustering, which means that the data collected from the 5G testbeds is formatted, statistically analyzed (generating average, standard deviation, and 95th percentile values), and published on different topics that can be consumed by any Network Application.
- **[NEW]** Network data publishing: For the purpose of publishing data, VA7 is creating different topics that provide access to real-time and historical data for different network metrics collected in the three trial sites. In addition, discovery of available topics is also possible, as VA7 allows Network Applications to subscribe to the topic called 'va7/data topics', on which they can find out the available topics that will be relevant for them. The subscription to the topics is part of the design of the subscribing Network Application itself.

All the features presented above are new, as this Network Application is for the first time described in this deliverable.

²² <https://gitlab.slicenet.oteresearch.gr/vital-5g-netapps/data-stream-organization>

5.8.2 Software Architecture

The functional components of VA7 are illustrated in Figure 62, including the internal components such as Network Data Collector, Network Data Processor, and Network Data Publisher, as well as the interaction between the Network Data Collector and Centralized Monitoring Platform. As described in Section 5.8.1, Network Data Collector is dynamically collecting real-time network data by subscribing to the monitoring platform. Further, Network Data Processor is processing the data collected from the testbeds, making statistical analysis, and providing alarms and notifications for the other Network Applications, thereby making them network-aware. Finally, Network Data Publisher is publishing the aforementioned data to different topics, to which the network-aware Network Applications can subscribe.

Figure 62: Functional components of VA7, and interaction between VA7 and other systems.

The implementation of each of the aforementioned features is illustrated through workflow presented in Figure 63.

5.8.3 APIs and Interfaces

The external interface with the Centralized Monitoring platform is enabled through ZeroMQ subscription mechanism, while the interface towards the Network Applications is maintained through publishing data through Zenoh. In the case of Antwerp testbed and current implementation of VA7, it is communicating with the local

monitoring system via REST requests, sending GET request to discover the available topics to which it can subscribe.

Figure 63: Generalized VA7 workflows.

5.8.4 Deployment

The VA7 Network Application is currently deployed in the Antwerp 5G testbed, and it is available both as Docker and VM image. It is important to note that the same Network Application can be deployed in other trial sites, i.e., other VITAL-5G testbeds.

5.8.5 Software assets

This Network Application provides access to network data to 3rd party experimenter Network Applications as well, and as such, the support for interfacing (subscription and discovery of different topics) will be provided by IMEC.

5.9 VS1 Indoor Robot Navigation & Coordination with Task Planning

The VS1 Network Application used along with VA1 “Distribution sensor ingestion and automation” provides the necessary functionality to allow Autonomous Guided Vehicles (AGVs) to perform autonomous transport operations within a warehouse.

5.9.1 Final Release Features

The VS1 Network Application provides the following features:

- **[UPDATED]** Logistics Lifecycle Management Service (Logistics LCM): API providing access to pending transportation jobs and warehouse products.
- AGV Task Allocation and Planning: Facilitating task planning by mapping high level messages to the internal behaviour trees information understood by the AGVs. The messages are sent through the MQTT broker provided by VA1.
- **[UPDATED]** Deployed a telemetry station hosting a warehouse simulator which interacts with the VS1 Network application to simulate workers fulfilling orders in a warehouse. The simulated data are published over the deployed 5G network and runs 24/7 which allows the collection of metrics for evaluation and optimization. Additionally, the telemetry station includes a camera sending video to the Video service exposed by the VS2 network application. This has been used to further stress the 5G network and collect metrics for video bitrate and latency.

Figure 64: Sequence of messages exchanged between the AGV and the Logistics LCM component.

Figure 65: WINGSChariot Screenshot – 2D Floorplan and Warehouse Simulator.

5.9.2 Software Architecture

Figure 66: Components of VS1 and communication with VA1 and remote assets.

The LLCM and Planning components described in the previous section utilize the services offered by the VA1 Network Application to communicate with remote devices such as Autonomous Guided Vehicles (AGVs). More details about the edge equipment are listed in the Deployment section below.

5.9.3 APIs and Interfaces

The Logistics LCM (LLCM) component provides access to pending jobs and product placements to support the autonomous operation by the AGV. The main API endpoints are listed in Figure 67.

Method	Endpoint	Description
GET	/api/v1/orders/active-orders	Get active orders
POST	/api/v1/orders/create-orders	Post a list of orders
GET	/api/v1/orders/next-order/{picker_id}	Get next order to be picked
GET	/api/v1/orders/order-details/{order_id}	Get details for a specific order
POST	/api/v1/orders/order-optimal-route/{order_id}	Return the optimal route for a specific order based on the location provided
GET	/api/v1/orders/orders-generator/{status}	Enable or disable auto order generator
POST	/api/v1/orders/update-order/{order_id}	Update an order
products		
POST	/api/v1/products/create-products	Post a new product. If the product exists it will be updated (A patch request must be added)
GET	/api/v1/products/product-info/{product_code}	Get product details
GET	/api/v1/products/product-locations/{product_code}	Get the locations a product is stored
GET	/api/v1/products/symbolic-location/{symbolic_location}	Get symbolic location
POST	/api/v1/products/update-product/{product_code}	Update a product

Figure 67: Logistics LCM API endpoints.

Third parties can interact with the LLCM interfaces exposed through VA1, although it becomes more useful when combined with the rest of the UC3 services. The API is also used by the developed simulators which can be accessed by third parties through the messages they exchange through the MQTT broker.

5.9.4 Deployment

The VS1 Network Application provides functionality to the AGV deployed in the warehouse. The AGV has been connected to the 5G Network as depicted in the architecture diagram in the previous section. Along with the AGV, warehouse device simulators have been deployed to assist in collecting KPIs (such as bandwidth and latency) since it is not feasible to have the AGV deployed in the operational environment of the warehouse 24/7. The details of the AGV are listed below:

- ClearPath Boxer 2.4(open-source firmware, ROS/ROS2 compatible).
 - Capabilities: Move forward (speed up to 2m/s), move backwards, rotate, lift (~10cm).
 - Sensors: Laser Scanner (LiDAR), RGBD camera, Inertial Measurement Unit, Motor Encoders.
- Custom cart designed for carrying EU pallets (120x80cm).

Along with the AGV, a telemetry station is deployed based on Raspberry PI 4 with DHT22 Temp/Humidity sensors attached and a USB Camera.

The components of VS1 are provided as a Virtual Machine image instantiated in the Athens testbed. It is important to note that the same Network Application can be deployed on other trial sites, i.e., other VITAL-5G testbeds.

5.9.5 Software assets

The VS1 Network Application does not share any code or features with previous projects such as 5G-EVE. It is part of the WINGS Chariot platform developed by WINGS ICT Solutions and is covered by a proprietary license which allows usage within the scope of VITAL-5G, both by the VITAL-5G partners and third-party experimenters.

The VS1 Network Application is offered as a Virtual Machine image at <https://share.wings-ict-solutions.dev/vital5g/>. Software keys and guidance are provided to partners for onboarding the VM in the VITAL-5G platform.

5.10 VS2 Human-robot Collaboration

This Network Application along with the VA1 “Distribution sensor ingestion and automation” provides the necessary functionality to allow AGVs to perform the follow-me function and to carry out tasks collaboratively with human operators.

5.10.1 Final Release Features

The Network application provides the following features:

- Human Machine Interface (HMI) to aid AGV in following a human operator at a close distance. This includes setting the AGV into a “Follow-me” mode and exposing the results of the computational offloading component to the VA1 Network Application for two-way communication with the onsite equipment.
- **[UPDATED]** Computational offloading: The core of the follow-me functionality is based on the Terabee™ ultrawide band positioning system. However, the computational offloading module can help to increase the accuracy of this operation by making available a more sophisticated positioning system. This includes a “Leg Detector” module which provides an estimate for the position of a human in front of an AGV using Lidar data and improves the localization accuracy compared to when using only the Terabee™ positioning system.

Figure 68: “Leg Detector” showcased on UC3 Trials.

- **[UPDATED]** Video controller and streaming server assisting a human operator for remote control of the AGV. The video service has been integrated with VA1 and video players have been exposed to the WINGS Chariot web interface for monitoring and remote control of the AGV. The video service now

includes a measurement of the video latency through a custom implementation which passes timestamps along with the video frames.

Figure 6g: Streaming Video from the onboard AGV camera for teleoperation.

5.10.2 Software Architecture

The Human Machine Interface and computational offloading features are enabled using custom components and utilize the services offered by the VA1 Network Application to interact with remote devices such as AGVs.

The video service exposes separate external interfaces in order to receive video frames from onsite devices and send video frames to clients with low latency. A ZeroMQ [18] server lies in the core of the Video streaming server while a custom video controller orchestrates the connection establishment.

More details about the edge equipment are listed in the Deployment section.

Figure 70: Components of VS2 and communication with VA1 and remote assets.

5.10.3 APIs and Interfaces

The computation services offered by VS2 are exposed through the VA1 MQTT and HTTP interfaces.

The Video Controller service of the HMI assist component exposes the API endpoints depicted in Figure 71.

Chariot Streaming Controller 0.1.0 OAS3

/api/v1/openapi.json

devices		^
POST	/devices/register	Registers a new device
POST	/devices/unregister/{device_id}	Removes a registered device
POST	/devices/connect	Sets connected status to a registered device.
POST	/devices/disconnect/{device_id}	Sets disconnected status to a registered device.
GET	/devices/status	Returns the current status of all registered devices.
GET	/devices/{device_id}/status	Returns the current status of a specific device.
POST	/devices/heartbeat	Devices keep sending post request to verify they are up
resources		∨
streaming		^
POST	/streaming/stream/{device_id}	Returns the streaming url of the requested device
POST	/streaming/stop-stream/{device_id}	Returns the streaming url of the requested device
servers		^
POST	/servers/register	Registers a new server
POST	/servers/unregister/{server_id}	Removes a registered server
POST	/servers/connect	Sets connected status to a registered server.
POST	/servers/disconnect/{server_id}	Sets disconnected status to a registered server.
GET	/servers/status	Returns the current status of all registered servers.
GET	/servers/{server_id}/status	Returns the current status of a specific server.
POST	/servers/heartbeat	Servers keep sending post request to verify they are up

Figure 71: HMI assist - Video Controller service endpoints.

The API allows a device to be registered for sending video to the Video streaming service, and clients (such as a web browser) to turn on/off the stream and receive the video frames for playback. The API is accessible to third parties although it currently requires coding to handle the connection establishment with the video controller and streaming server. The WINGSChariot application interface exposed by VA1 makes it easier to interact with the service.

5.10.4 Deployment

The VS2 Network Application provides functionality to the AGV deployed to the warehouse. The AGV has been connected to the 5G Network as depicted in the previous diagram. The details of the AGV are listed below:

- ClearPath Boxer 2.4(open-source firmware, ROS/ROS2 compatible)
 - Capabilities: Move forward (speed up to 2m/s), move backwards, rotate, lift (~10cm)
 - Sensors: Laser Scanner (LiDAR), RGBD camera, Inertial Measurement Unit, Motor Encoders.
- Custom cart designed for carrying EU pallets (120x80cm)

Along with the AGV, a relative positioning system (Terabee™ “Follow-me”) is carried by a human operator to assist during the follow-me operation to support the proximity-based collaboration with the AGV.

The components of VS2 are provided as a Virtual Machine image instantiated in the Athens testbed. It is important to note that the same Network Application can be deployed on other trial sites, i.e., other VITAL-5G testbeds.

5.10.5 Software assets

The VS2 Network Application does not share any code or features with previous projects such as 5G-EVE. It is part of the WINGS Chariot platform developed by WINGS ICT Solutions and is covered by a proprietary license which allows usage within the scope of VITAL-5G, both by the VITAL-5G partners and third-party experimenters.

The VS2 Network Application is offered as a Virtual Machine image at <https://share.wings-ict-solutions.dev/vital5g/>. Software keys and guidance are provided to partners for onboarding the VM in the VITAL-5G platform.

5.11 VS3 AI/ML-based Automated Fault Detection and Predictive Maintenance

5.11.1 Final Release Features

The AI/ML-based Automated Fault Detection is a Network Application focused on providing intelligent mechanisms to predict required maintenance operations on the T&L infrastructure. In this sense, this Network Application complements the functionality provided by VA4, providing specialized data processing algorithms for the detection of behaviors in the technical sensors and systems of the warehouse (or the vessel, depending on the target deployment) which could automatically trigger the maintenance operations, or warn the technical operators to perform manual interventions. Furthermore, the events and outcomes identified by this Network Application are published in the common datastore offered by the IoT Management Platform (VA4) in order to be available for other Network Applications to consume and possibly trigger further events. The target is to improve the T&L infrastructure availability and improve the overall planning of maintenance operations. In this case the aim is set on generating alerts using the AGV of the Greek testbed, based on the AGV onboard sensor data (e.g., tire pressure, humidity levels, etc.).

5.11.2 Software Architecture

This Network Application has been completely released in this final release. This includes the software assets for the execution of algorithms and a pre-trained prediction algorithm which would raise an event to trigger an AGV maintenance operation (e.g., tire change).

Figure 72: VS3 Internal Architecture.

In Figure 72 we depict the internal architecture of this Network Application, where the functionality of each subcomponent is as follows:

- **Pre-trained ML models:** This component uses TensorFlow [22] loaded trained models from a MinIO [8] storage, externally accessible by the Network Application Admin for updates on model versions. The Tensorflow serving can be called through an API by the Anomaly detector to produce an inference from input data.
- **Anomaly detector:** Interfaces with the IoT datastore from VA4 for historical data to determine the appropriate models to deploy at run-time. This component performs the inference over the historical data on the available trained models and stores the results in MinIO to be retrieved and displayed on a GUI. Furthermore, this module also performs AI-based anomaly detection using live data retrieved through the VA4 data stream and reported to the Fault predictor subcomponent.
- **Fault predictor:** Evaluates the run-time anomaly in combination with past anomaly occurrences pulled from the time series database to determine that a predicted fault is imminent.
- **Predictive Maintenance Planner:** Provides a dashboard and a GUI to access the data and the outcomes of the Fault Predictor.

5.11.3 APIs and Interfaces

This Network Application offers APIs to: (i) Select and customize the prediction algorithm; (ii) Retrieve information regarding the algorithm prediction outcomes in terms of suggested maintenance operations. The API is available in OpenAPI format in the project software repository.

5.11.4 Deployment

This Network Application leverages VA4, as described in D2.1 [3], for the retrieval of the IoT sensor data, as illustrated in Figure 73. In terms of 5G connectivity, this means that this Network Application depends on the deployment mechanism used for the deployment of VA4.

Figure 73: Deployment of VS3.

5.11.5 Software assets

VS3 is made available as a single VM snapshot (qcow2 format) through the following FTP:

Server: mercurio.nextworks.it

Port: 9292

Files: Vital5G_VS3_aiml_based_prediction.qcow2

5.12 VS4 Technical Data Visualization

The Technical Data Visualization Network Application developed by NXW, as described in D2.1 [3], aims to simplify the technical operation and management of T&L facility (e.g warehouse, smart factories), by providing customized monitoring dashboards and panels to visualize the monitoring information and events collected by the IoT Management Platform (VA4). This Network Application is based on adaptations and re-packaging of software assets of NXW Symphony product portfolio, which leverages Grafana [21] and other internal software assets to present the data to the end users in a friendly manner. We refer to D2.1 [3] for further details.

5.12.1 Final Release Features

This Network Application has been entirely released in this final release. In Figure 74 we depict one of the customized dashboards of the Network Application.

Figure 74: VS4 Technical Data Visualization GUI.

5.12.2 Software Architecture

In Figure 75 we depict the internal architecture of VS4 and the interfaces towards other Network Applications. As described in the picture this Network Application is composed by two internal functional blocks: (i) Visualization dashboards, which exposes a HTTP based GUI for the visualization of the customized monitoring dashboards based on the information stored in VA4; (ii) Dashboard configurator module, implementing a REST based server and a HTTP based GUI for the design and definition of the monitoring dashboards.

Figure 75: VS4 Internal architecture.

5.12.3 APIs and Interfaces

This Network Application exposes an HTTP based GUI for the visualization, and design of the custom monitoring dashboards, and a REST based interface for the creation and configuration. This latter interface is available in OpenAPI format in the project repository.

5.12.4 Deployment

In Figure 76 we provide a deployment-oriented representation of VS4, originally established in D2.1 [3]. As depicted in the figure, VS4 leverages on the 5G connectivity used by VA4, which depends on the deployment scenario as described in Section 5.5.4 (which can be attached directly, or through another Network Application).

Figure 76: VS4 Deployment.

5.12.5 Software assets

VS4 is made available as a single VM snapshot (qcow2 format) through the following FTP:

Server: mercurio.nextworks.it

Port: 9292

Files: Vital5G_VS4_visualization.qcow2

5.13 VS5 Monitoring Dashboard

VS5 is a web-based application which aims to provide assistance to the captains of vessels. This dashboard provides better situational awareness by providing Artificial Intelligence-enabled tools such as optimized speed or waypoint following. VS5 is a monitoring dashboard that was previously developed, tested & integrated with other Network Applications (VS8, VS7).

5.13.1 Final Release Features

The final release contains:

- Camera view of the vessel (previously protected by password that can only be accessed by Seafar) accessible for the captain;
- Real-time location of the vessel on an interactive 3D map, now also integrating the results from VA5 to show the objects as well as the waypoints calculated in VS6;
- A view that shows the result of VS7 on the dashboard and allows for the user of the dashboard to interact with VS7 (optimal speed visualization);
- **[NEW]** The final feature of this monitoring tool is the integration with network applications of waypoint following (VS6) and object detection (VA5), using Zenoh instead of ZeroMQ for communication. The necessary integration relevant to dashboard (VS5) has been implemented.

5.13.2 Software Architecture

Figure 77: VS5 Network Application and the communication with other Network Applications.

The necessary connections communicated with IMEC are as follows:

- Reading from VS6 (zmq)
- Reading from VA5(zmq)
- Reading from VS8 (zmq)
- Reading from VS7 (zmq)
- Publishing to VS6(zmq)
- Publishing to VS7 (REST API)

Zenoh [17] was utilized as it solves discoverability issue between Network Applications.

In the new version of VS5, the solution for utilization of a boat was considered and camera streams were shown in VS5 as well.

5.13.3 APIs and Interfaces

3rd parties can utilize the dashboard for their use cases.

GNSS data of an automated vessel navigating in Flemish waterways has been collected and provided for 3rd party experimentation.

5.13.4 Deployment

Seafar has collected data from an automated vessel for algorithms development by IMEC. This dataset includes synchronized data of AIS, GNSS, camera and radar. These data sets are used for VS6 and VA5 network application development.

The integration and communication between different network applications has been tested by using a boat with real time GNSS and radar data collection.

5.13.5 Software assets

The monitoring dashboard is not open source, but the interfacing and integration with this component are facilitated through the use of Zenoh communication tool. It could be also shared with the 3rd party experimenters.

5.14 VS6 Assisted Vessel Navigation

The Assisted Vessel Navigation Network Application assists the captain of a vessel with navigation suggestions, consisting of global trajectory prediction. This Network Application will be deployed in the Antwerp testbed area.

5.14.1 Final Release Features

The final release of this Network Application includes the following features:

- Based on a real-time received vessel information (position, speed, heading), desired destination, obstacle information and knowledge of the navigation area, VS6 determines a path to the destination (global planning) and finds an optimized local path (local planning).
- **[NEW]** In addition, a new communication mechanism was also added in this release, using the Zenoh library [17], as an alternative to the previous ZeroMQ [18] mechanism.
- **[NEW]** A new essential feature was added to this release of the VS6 Network Application: the automatic generation of the static (waterway) maps. Previously, the application was relying on internal storage to access static map information. This prevented path planning in real time in all geographical locations, because the stored map would not be automatically updated. In this release, a new waterway map is generated whenever the relevant quantities (e.g., the captain goal) are newly received and thus updated. The generated map is used to carry out global path planning and, by combination with the obstacle map, to generate the dynamic map. All the necessary input to the local planning is thereby ensured.

5.14.2 Software Architecture

This new Static map generation module mentioned previously takes as input the current vessel position and the current goal position, and queries OpenStreetMap [23] via the OSMnx [24] Python library. This data is used to generate a binary map of the current sailing area based on image settings requirements (such as the resolution) from the VS6 configuration.

The working principle of the other functional blocks of the application are summarized below:

- The Map interlacing module combines the obstacle information received from the VS5 Network Application with the static map information to generate the dynamic map which will be fed to the Local path planner.
- The Global path planner component receives the necessary vessel parameters (latitude, longitude, heading, speed) and the end goal information (latitude, longitude). Together with the static map of the sailing area (image), it calculates positions (latitudes, longitudes) of intermediate goals up to the end goal. If called for the first time with a new end goal or new map data, the intermediate goal will be cached in the internal storage.
- Local path planner generates a set of candidate trajectories in the Frenet coordinate frame and rates them by a cost function to produce the unique trajectory suggestion (sequence of waypoints). During local planning, vessel data and static map data are processed to produce waypoint suggestions, which are updated depending on goal information.

Figure 76 displays the functional architecture of the VS6 Network Application.

Figure 78: VS6 functional architecture.

Visuals of output examples of VS6 are provided in Figure 77.

Figure 79: VS6 Visuals of output examples: Static map combined with dynamic obstacles, global path planning (blue circles), local planning (green circles and red dot).

5.14.3 APIs and Interfaces

In the final release, VS6 has the following interfaces:

- With the Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessels (VS8) Network Application, which sends the necessary vessel data.
- With the Real-time digital twin (VA5), which send the obstacle map and the associated metadata.
- With the Remote vessel monitoring (VS5), which sends the captain’s goal instruction and receives in turn the trajectory waypoints after the planning calculation.

Data exchanges with other Network Applications are ensured by the ZeroMQ or Zenoh library.

Figure 78 displays the network architecture of the VS6 Network Application.

Figure 80: VS6 network architecture.

5.14.4 Deployment

VS6 is made available as a virtual machine instantiated on IMEC servers in the Antwerp testbed.

5.14.5 Software assets

The access to the Assisted vessel navigation Network Application is restricted to the output trajectory waypoints.

5.15 VS7 Navigation Speed Optimizer

As described in previous deliverables, VS7 is responsible for calculating in real time the optimal navigation speed for a vessel based on geodata and planning data in UC1.

5.15.1 Final Release Features

The final version of VS7 includes the following:

- VS7 functions as a back-end REST API, whereby clients can transmit data through HTTPS using a JSON format;
- Full integration with VS8 to receive the geodata of the vessel;
- Full integration with VS5 to receive the planning data and return the computed optimal navigation speed;
- **[NEW]** Communication between VS7 and VS8 and VS5 will occur now over Zenoh [17], instead of ZeroMQ [18], as was stated in previous deliverables. This change was made to resolve the discoverability challenges between static and dynamic IPs, as explained in further detail in Section 5.15 about VS8;
- All API traffic is encrypted using Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificates;
- Open Authorization (OAuth) v2 is used for authentication purposes.

5.15.2 Software Architecture

Figure 81: VS7 Software Architecture.

As described in previous deliverables and visualized in Figure 79, VS7 collects data from client applications (i.e., VS5 and VS8) and an inland navigation routing API (i.e. VisuRIS), and uses that to calculate the optimal navigation speed for a vessel. The geodata from VS8 and the desired time of arrival from VS5 are used by the NSO algorithm to calculate the optimal speed based on the distance to be sailed and the remaining time. The speed is then published on a queue and can be subscribed to by VS5 for integration into the vessel navigation assistance dashboard. The dependencies of the above-mentioned network applications are visualized in Figure 8068.

Figure 82: VS7 Network Application dependencies.

5.15.3 APIs and Interfaces

As described in D2.3, the computed optimal navigation speed can be retrieved in two ways: by making a call to the REST API or by querying the queue. The VS7 object contains the following data:

```
{
  startIsrs: string|null,
  endIsrs: string|null,
  eta: string|null,
  routeLength: number,
  optimalSpeedKmh: number,
  optimalSpeedKnots: number,
  lastUpdateTimestamp: number|null,
};
```

Where:

- startIsrs: ISRS code of the current location of the vessel
- endIsrs: ISRS code of the destination of the vessel's trip
- eta: Time the vessel is expected at the destination
- routeLength: Length of the route the vessel has to sail
- optimalSpeedKmh: The calculated optimal speed in kilometer per hour
- optimalSpeedKnots: The calculated optimal speed in knots
- lastUpdateTimestamp: Timestamp of the latest update

The destination can be set by making a POST request to the `/destination` REST endpoint. VS7 expects the data in the following format:

```
{
  "latitude": 51.254887,
  "longitude": 4.231544,
```

```
"desiredTimeOfArrivalUtc": "2012-07-09T19:22:09.1440844Z"  
}
```

5.15.4 Deployment

VS7 is deployed as a containerized Network Application on the Network Application platform on IMEC premises within the 5G testbed.

5.15.5 Software assets

VS7 is available as a Docker image on Gitlab²³. Third-party experimenters can use the application as is, adapt it to their needs or build upon it, as the source code is available in the repository under an open source license (GPLv3).

5.16 VS8 Onboard Data Collection & Interfacing for Vessels

The Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessels is the vertical-specific Network Application responsible for collection and processing of onboard data collected from the vessels, such as Tercofin II or any other boat used for the trialling activities and demo purposes in UC1. So far in the project, VS8 has been used for collecting Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) data (i.e., speed, heading and location). This data is being collected over the 5G network using an URLLC slice. The purpose of VS8 is to collect data from the boat/vessel in a real-time manner, and to share the collected data with the other Network Applications in UC1, or any 3rd party Network Application that may need GNSS data or similar data types.

5.16.1 Final Release Features

The final release features include:

- Collection of data from the boat/vessel in a real-time manner and sharing the collected data with the other Network Applications in UC1, or any 3rd party Network Application that may need GNSS data or similar data types.
- **[NEW]** Due to the discoverability challenges between the vessel maintained by Seafar and Network Applications running on the IMEC Edge computing infrastructure, and no possibility to use the static IP on the Telenet side, we have reconfigured the data collection mechanism for VS8. Instead of using ZeroMQ [18] as reported in previous WP2 deliverable, the final protocol is Zenoh Eclipse [17]. In particular, Zenoh is a pub/sub/query protocol unifying data in motion, data at rest and computations. The reconsideration of the data collection design choice resulted in choosing Zenoh for final implementation, due to its flexible and dynamic mechanism to discover data publishers and subscribers by only specifying the topic name, thus, with no need to know the IP address of the hosts.
- **[NEW]** Producing its own metrics related to CPU and memory load, and such values are being published from the local monitoring system on the Centralized monitoring platform, where the real-time analysis of VS8 performance can be tracked.

5.16.2 Software Architecture

All information related to VS8, i.e., its original release features, functional blocks, APIs, interfaces, deployment, and software assets, can be found also in D2.2 [4]. The latest overview of the software architecture is as shown in Figure 83:

- **The Device Specific Interface** block handles the data received from Tercofin II via the 5G network using a URLLC link. More information is provided in D2.2.
- **The data Manager block** is in charge of storing all received data from the **device specific interface**. More information is provided in D2.2.

²³ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vs7

- **The Data Storage block** stores all the received data coming from the **data manager block**. More information is provided in D2.2.
- **The public interface block** makes the received GNSS data available to other Network Applications using the pub/sub mechanism of Zenoh instead of ZeroMQ like written in D2.2.

Figure 83: VS8 software architecture and interaction with other Network Applications and the boat/vessel.

5.16.3 APIs and Interfaces

It is important to note that interfacing with VS8 is possible for any 3rd party Network Application that requires real-time GNSS data collection from the UE (either the vessel maintained by Seafar, or any other UE). In addition, to facilitate the process of interfacing with VS8, IMEC provides support in terms of setting up the necessary subscribers for the 3rd party Network Applications. This support includes the guidelines on the required installation and use of subscriber Python scripts. More information is provided in Deliverable D2.2 [4].

5.16.4 Deployment

Concerning the deployment, as described in D2.3 [5], VS8 is interacting both with the boat/vessel (uplink communication via 5G) and with each Network Application within UC1. It is available both as a VM image created for the purpose of deploying orchestrated VS8 deployments in OpenStack environment, and as a Docker image that can be easily spawned at any commodity server. The output of VS8, i.e., the processed vessel positioning data is published on a particular topic using Zenoh, to which Zenoh subscribers in VS5, VS6, and VS7, connect to. The updated deployment with Zenoh resolved various discoverability issues between Network Applications in UC1, which were previously handled using DNS. With this new setup, there is no longer a need to know either DNS names or IP addresses of other Network Applications, which makes the communication within the use case much more streamlined. In addition, the same design principle is required for any 3rd party Network Application interacting with Network Applications within UC1. However, the design and implementation will be further facilitated with the help from IMEC, as briefly described in Section 5.16.3.

5.16.5 Software assets

The final version of VS8 is available as a VM image, and as such it is accessible on the Gitlab repository²⁴. For more details on the implementation and software assets of VS8, see D2.2 [4].

5.17 VS9 Onboard Data Collection & Interfacing for NAVROM Vessel

This Network Application is responsible for collecting ship-related data from vessels in UC2 (i.e., AIS data, depth, engine, speed etc.), and is made available for other VITAL-5G Network Applications and 3rd party Network Applications. This Network Application collects data specific to the NAVROM vessel(s) used in UC2.

5.17.1 Final Release Features

The current release of VS9 supports the following data collected from vessel:

- [UPDATED] Depth sensor data
- [UPDATED] AIS data
- [UPDATED] Air quality data
- [UPDATED] Water quality data
- [UPDATED] Video stream data[NEW] GPS data.

5.17.2 Software Architecture

Figure 84: VS9 architecture.

Figure 84 illustrates the VS9 architecture. The main components of VS9 are:

1. Sensor data pre-processors (YOLO²⁵ and AIS²⁶) – capture the data from devices and create the JSON payload to be sent to MQTT broker via NodeRED
2. NodeRED based flow editor – connects with the testbed devices via the pre-processing blocks, gathers all the data from the sensors and publishes them in a specific JSON format to an MQTT.

²⁴ <https://gitlab.ilabt.imec.be/vital-5g/vs8-zenoh>

²⁵ <https://pjreddie.com/darknet/yolo/>

²⁶ [https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/OurWork/Safety/Documents/AIS/Resolution%20A.1106\(29\).pdf](https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/OurWork/Safety/Documents/AIS/Resolution%20A.1106(29).pdf)

3. MQTT Broker (EMQX²⁷)

The building blocks have been described in detail in D2.3 [5].

5.17.3 APIs and Interfaces

VS9 offers a Pub/Sub mechanism supporting data that is published from the testbed sensors to any interested party (via MQTT subscriber clients).

Table 8 shows the currently sent MQTT topics and payloads sent.

Table 7: MQTT topics and payloads sent by VS9.

#	MQTT topic	Payload
1	uc2/real/va6/mercur	{ "depth": 20 } } "TC": 27.03 "PRES": 101640 "HUM": 45.00 "LUX": 98 "O2": 213000 "CO": 0.6 }
2	uc2/real/va6/mercur/gps	{ "latitude": 45.4317493, "longitude": 28.0631285 }
3	uc2/real/va6/mercur/ais/#	{ "latituded": 45.4317497 "longitude": 28.0631289 "speed": 10 }
4	uc2/video	{ "pre-process": "process", "inference": "inference", "NMS per image": "NMS" }
5	uc2/real/va6/ponton	{ "depth": 22.13 } { "WT": 19.6 "SWIPH": 8,37 }
6	uc2/real/va6/ponton/ais/#	{ "latituded": 45.4317497 "longitude": 28.0631289 "speed": 10 }
7	uc2/backup/va6/mercur	{

²⁷ <https://www.emqx.io/>

		<pre> "depth": 20 } } "TC": 27.03 "PRES": 101640 "HUM": 45.00 "LUX": 98 "O2": 213000 "CO": 0.6 } </pre>
8	uc2/backup/va6/mercur/gps	<pre> { "latitude": 45.4317493, "longitude": 28.0631285 } </pre>
9	uc2/backup/va6/mercur/ais/#	<pre> { "latituded": 45.4317497 "longitude": 28.0631289 "speed": 10 } </pre>
10	uc2/backup/va6/ponton	<pre> { "depth": 22.13 } { "WT": 19.6 "SWIPH": 8,37 } </pre>
11	uc2/backup/va6/ponton/ais/#	<pre> { "latituded": 45.4317497 "longitude": 28.0631289 "speed": 10 } </pre>

The MQTT topics 'uc2/real/#' represent live data coming from the port area, while the topics 'uc2/backup/#' represents past data that is cycled through VA6, and made available on the broker for debugging and testing purposes.

5.17.4 Deployment

The VS9 is deployed on an eMBB network slice implementation.

The following IoT devices are used.

- **AIS transponder (SAAB R4 or Periskal PM-1)** – that provides data about the type of ship, the position of the ship, the speed of the ship, the angle made relative to the North direction, the type of voyage to be made, the estimated time to the end of that trip.
- **ACTISENSE DST 2 converter** – device to which the depth sensor is connected. Basically, it transmits pulses with a frequency of 200kHz (in the field of ultrasound) to the depth sensor (Airmar SS505). The ultrasonic wave generated by the sensor propagates to the bottom of the water.
- **PLC (Siemens IoT 20xx or Raspberry PI)** – is a digital or analog signal amplifier? that outputs digital signals converted into a protocol recognized by its peripherals (e.g., 5G router).
- **Depth sensor type Airmar SS505**
- **GPS** – a system composed of a GPS antenna and an Adafruit traductor for processing the signals, for sending global location data.

5.17.5 Software assets

The software components of VS9 produced in the project will be released as open source, and code is available in the project GitLab repository²⁸.

The install folder in the VS9 repository contains the docker files which allow to build and execute this module using Docker.

²⁸ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/data-collection-navrom

6 Conclusions

This section concludes the implementation work taken place throughout the work package 2. To sum up, in this deliverable the new and improved features and final versions of the VITAL-5G components and the consortium's Network Applications are presented.

Furthermore, authors have reported not only on the final functionalities developed, but also on their evolution compared to previous releases included in D2.1-D2.3 [3][4][5] and -if applicable- to baseline applications and components from previous works and projects.

Indeed, the document presented the final delivery of 15 network applications catering to three use cases and 14 platform components (some of them new) and in one case moved a Network Application functionality into the core platform capabilities to increase impact and usability. In fact, 3 components were fully implemented for D2.4 (with one originally planned as a network application but integrated as a platform component). In addition to this, 2 Network Applications are fully released in D2.4 and most of them were updated and improved upon.

As this work package is concluded with the submission of deliverable 2.4, the VITAL-5G Platform and the Network Applications integration is taking place within WP3 and the WP4 will cover the trial results that will validate the work done within this WP.

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- [24] Boeing, G. 2017. OSMnx: New Methods for Acquiring, Constructing, Analyzing, and Visualizing Complex Street Networks (<https://geoffboeing.com/publications/osmnx-complex-street-networks/>). Computers, Environment and Urban Systems 65, 126-139. doi:10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2017.05.004

Annex I: Example Network Application Blueprint

The following JSON provides the blueprint of VA4 to use as reference and example to design other Network Applications. The project also provides a repository which can be used to retrieve updated examples of the other project Network Applications²⁹.

```
{
  "name": "VA4 IoT Management Platform",
  "description": "NetApp for collection of IoT data and actuators control for heterogeneous and configurable devices, with mechanisms for unified data modelling, monitoring, and reporting. ",
  "version": "1.0",
  "vnfPackagePath": "http://nextworks.it/symphony",
  "applicationMetrics": [
    {
      "metricId": "alarm_rate",
      "name": "Alarm Rate",
      "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
      "metricGraphType": "LINE",
      "unit": "alarms per second",
      "interval": "10"
    }
  ],
  "infrastructureMetrics": [
    {
      "type": "RELIABILITY",
      "metricId": "reliability",
      "name": "reliability",
      "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
      "unit": "percentage",
      "interval": "10",
      "metricGraphType": "LINE",
      "componentIds": []
    },
    {
      "type": "LATENCY_USERPLANE_RTT",
      "metricId": "latency",
      "name": "latency",
      "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
      "unit": "seconds",
      "interval": "10",
      "metricGraphType": "LINE",
      "componentIds": []
    },
    {
      "type": "USER_DATA_RATE_UPLINK",
      "metricId": "uplink_datarate",

```

²⁹ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vital-5g-netapp-blueprints

```

"name": "uplink_datarate",
"metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
"unit": "seconds",
"interval": "10",
"metricGraphType": "LINE",
"componentIds": []
},
{
"type": "USER_DATA_RATE_DOWNLINK",
"metricId": "downlink_datarate",
"name": "uplink_datarate",
"metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
"unit": "seconds",
"interval": "10",
"metricGraphType": "LINE",
"componentIds": []
},
{
"type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
"metricId": "memory_usage",
"name": "memory_usage",
"metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
"unit": "seconds",
"interval": "10",
"metricGraphType": "LINE",
"componentIds": [
  "IoTAlertAndEventManager",
  "MessageBroker"
],
  "vnfReference": "vmReference"
},
{
"type": "DISK_USAGE",
"metricId": "disk_usage",
"name": "memory_usage",
"metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
"unit": "seconds",
"interval": "10",
"metricGraphType": "LINE",
"componentIds": [
  "IoTAlertAndEventManager",
  "MessageBroker",
  "DatastoreAndDashboard"
],
  "vnfReference": "vmReference"
}
],
"atomicComponents": [
{
  "componentId": "IoTAlertAndEventManager",

```

```
"minInstances": 0,
"maxInstances": 0,
"endPointsIds": [
  "alertEventManagerCore"
],
"placement": "CORE"
},
{
  "componentId": "IoTSupervisor",
  "minInstances": 0,
  "maxInstances": 0,
  "endPointsIds": [
    "IoTSupervisorData"
  ],
  "placement": "CORE"
},
{
  "componentId": "MessageBroker",
  "minInstances": 0,
  "maxInstances": 0,
  "endPointsIds": [
    "messageBrokerCore"
  ],
  "placement": "CORE"
},
{
  "componentId": "DatastoreAndDashboard",
  "minInstances": 0,
  "maxInstances": 0,
  "endPointsIds": [
    "datastoreDashboardCore",
    "datastoreDashboardQuery"
  ],
  "placement": "CORE"
},
{
  "componentId": "RestController",
  "minInstances": 0,
  "maxInstances": 0,
  "endPointsIds": [
    "RestControllerMgmt"
  ],
  "placement": "CORE"
}
],
"type": "SERVICE",
"specLevel": "VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC",
"accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
"configurableParameters": {
  "dashboard_port": "PORT OF THE DASHBOARD"
```

```

},
"serviceParameters": {},
"providedInterfaceSpec": [
{
  "interfaceServiceSpecId": "IoTManagementPlatformMgmt",
  "name": "IoTManagementPlatformMgmt",
  "version": "1.0",
  "protocol": "HTTP",
  "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
  "dataFormat": "JSON",
  "attachedSpecifications": [
    {
      "file": "softwaredoc/IoTManagementPlatformMgmtInterface.json",
      "format": "OPEN_API"
    }
  ],
  "endpointIds": [
    "RestControllerMgmt"
  ],
  "protocolParams": {}
},
{
  "interfaceServiceSpecId": "IoTDeviceDataProvider",
  "name": "IoTDeviceDataProvider",
  "version": "1.0",
  "protocol": "MQTT",
  "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
  "dataFormat": "JSON",
  "attachedSpecifications": [
    {
      "file": "apis/IoTManagementPlatformMessages.txt",
      "format": "DOCUMENTATION"
    }
  ],
  "role": "PROVIDER",
  "endpointIds": [
    "IotSupervisorData"
  ],
  "protocolParams": {}
},
{
  "interfaceServiceSpecId": "SymphonyDatastoreDashboard",
  "name": "SymphonyDatastoreDashboard",
  "version": "1.0",
  "protocol": "HTTP",
  "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
  "dataFormat": "JSON",
  "attachedSpecifications": [
    {
      "file": "softwaredoc/symphonDatastoreOpenAPI.json",

```

```

    "format": "OPEN_API"
  }
],
"endpointIds": [
  "dashboardDatastoreQuery"
],
"protocolParams": {}
}
],
"requiredInterfaceSpec": [],
"requiredEquipments": [
  {
    "requiredEquipmentId": "iotSensor",
    "type": "SENSOR",
    "accessLevel": "READ",
    "location": "AREA_ID",
    "description": "IoT_Supervisor",
    "interfaceProtocol": "MQTT",
    "mandatory": true,
    "exposedAccessLevel": "PRIVATE"
  }
],
"useCase": "test",
"testbed": "ATHENS",
"softwareLicenses": [
  {
    "softwareLicenseId": "symphonyLicense",
    "openLicense": false,
    "licenseFile": "licenses/symphonyLicense.txt",
    "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
    "componentIds": []
  }
],
"connectivityServices": [
  {
    "connectivityServiceId": "IoTManagementPlatformInternal",
    "endPointIds": [
      "messageBrokerCore",
      "datastoreDashboardCore",
      "alertEventManagerCore"
    ],
    "external": false,
    "management": false
  }
],
"endPoints": [
  {
    "endPointId": "alertEventManager",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": true,

```

```
"mobileConnection": false,
"radioAccessTechnology": null,
"coverageArea": null
},
{
  "endPointId": "datastoreDashboardQuery",
  "type": "EXTERNAL",
  "management": true,
  "mobileConnection": false,
  "radioAccessTechnology": null,
  "coverageArea": null
},
{
  "endPointId": "messageBrokerCore",
  "type": "INTERNAL",
  "management": false,
  "mobileConnection": false,
  "radioAccessTechnology": null,
  "coverageArea": null
},
{
  "endPointId": "IotSupervisorData",
  "type": "EXTERNAL",
  "management": true,
  "mobileConnection": true,
  "sliceProfile": [
    {
      "sliceProfileType": "URLLC",
      "profileParams": {
        "availability": 99,
        "latency": 60,
        "expDataRateUL": 100,
        "expDataRateDL": 100
      }
    }
  ],
  "radioAccessTechnology": "FIVE_G_NSA",
  "coverageArea": "AREA_ID"
}
],
"testCases": [],
"required5GCoreServices": []
}
```

Annex II: 3rd party Network Applications

This section summarizes some representative Network Applications by 3rd parties in all VITAL-5G testbeds.

1.1 Network applications from the 3rd party experimenter Zinkworks

The VITAL-5G 3rd party experimenter Zinkworks is a global leader in innovation, with offices in three locations worldwide, headquartered in Athlone, Ireland. Zinkworks utilizes the latest cutting-edge technologies to provide R&D services to clients primarily in the Telecommunications and Financial sectors. This expertise has led to Zinkworks developing their own in-house R&D unit and are actively developing a range of products, particularly focused on solutions in the 5G Private Network telecoms space.

At the Port of Antwerp trial site, Zinkworks is delivering the AI-based prediction capability for supporting the Assisted Vessel Transport use case, thereby creating innovative solutions that will improve the efficiency, safety, and sustainability of port operations. In particular, Zinkworks have remodeled their Apps to Network Applications for this project to test their AI solution for predictive modeling, which is suitable either for enhancing RIC operations or for easy integration with UC1 Network Applications via REST APIs. The automated prediction models that will be deployed as Network Applications will help lower costs, increase efficiency on the network and support the sustainability goals by reducing resources and energy wastage.

1.1.1 Intelligent Mobility Management Network Application

One of the Network Applications that Zinkworks is developing in the context of the VITAL-5G project is aimed at creating intelligent mobility management based on 5G high-precision positioning. Cellular-based positioning based on 5G can provide flexible and diverse service innovations for a wide range of fields, delivering improved security, efficiency, and business benefits to enterprise users through in-depth integration with vertical industries.

For the purpose of developing this Network Application, mobility prediction model is using accurate historical locations of UEs (UC1 vessel) to predict future locations or trajectories. At the moment, the data used for creating the model is GNSS data collected from the vessel, and the plan is to leverage on the accurate position data collected from the 5G core Location Management Function (LMF), thus 5G parameters from LMF, including the GNSS parameters. Such an advanced Network Application capable of performing accurate positioning based on the 5G data will have a significant impact on improving radio resource management by optimizing handover operations based on the predicted positions of the users. The prediction process of the ML model can be integrated with a holistic positioning system and serve as an API in real time.

1.1.2 Network Traffic Prediction Network Application

Second Network Application that Zinkworks is designing and developing in their 3rd party experimentation is dedicated to the Network Traffic Prediction (NTP), focusing on predicting the future of network load and its behavior. The results of the NTP Network Application are valuable for a wide range of applications, such as QoS provisioning, fault detection, security attach detection, network resource optimization, adapting traffic demands in real-time, predicting traffic peak and off-peak times to optimize power resources.

For the development of this Network Application, Zinkworks is using AI/ML techniques that are more powerful for processing complex non-linear network data than traditional optimization techniques. In particular, neural network models will use the historical network data collected and shared by IMEC and Telenet, for the purpose of generating predictions for future network traffic load.

1.2 Network applications from the 3rd party experimenter DEDICAT 6G

DEDICAT 6G aims to develop a smart connectivity platform using artificial intelligence and blockchain techniques that will enable 6G networks to combine the existing communication infrastructure with novel distribution of intelligence (data, computation, and storage) at the edge to allow not only flexible, but also energy efficient

realisation of the envisaged real-time experience. DEDICAT 6G focuses on four use cases: Smart warehousing, Enhanced experiences, Public Safety and Smart Highway. The use cases pilot the developed solutions via simulations and demonstrations in laboratory environments, and larger field evaluations exploiting various assets and testing facilities. The results are expected to show significant improvements in terms of intelligent network load balancing and resource allocation, extended connectivity, enhanced security, privacy and trust and human-machine interactions.

DEDICAT6G is interested in deploying their smart warehousing use case as a set of Network applications that provide the required service when combining them. Furthermore, they are interested in exploiting the network-related data collected from the 5G testbed to validate their algorithms for intelligence distribution, coverage extension and enhanced security and trust. In order to achieve this, they will deploy and test the following 2 components as Network Applications over the VITAL-5G platform. The Smart Warehousing use case comprises of two AGVs (Locobots) having a custom lift ability for bringing ordered products to the user. Both AGVs have ROS1/2 bridges and containerized docker microservices running on them.

1.2.1 DEDICAT 6G Controller

The AGVs communicate with the so-called DEDICAT 6G controller through fast Data Distribution Service (DDS) Discovery. This controller essentially facilitates communication of the AGVs/robots deployed over the 5G network with the user interfaces (i.e., the Warehouse Manager dashboard and the worker mobile app). For example, information sent to the Warehouse Manager dashboard includes AGV positioning/movement, camera feed and AGV status (e.g., battery level, CPU and RAM usage). The network application enables role and task assignment to individual robots to realise autonomous and collaborative applications. High network reliability is an important factor for the Controller Network application.

1.2.2 DEDICAT6G Intelligence Distribution Network application

The Intelligence Distribution Algorithm is responsible for (re-)distributing services dynamically to the network's nodes (AGVs, cloud nodes) for overcoming possible increase of network latency or possible unavailability of an AGV, while also considering power consumption on the robots. The network application retrieves important KPIs and utilizes facilities supported by the Virtual infrastructure to request changes to the scaling and placement characteristics of the backend services.

1.3 Network applications from the 3rd party experimenter diTTo BV

diTTo BV delivers products and services for Digital Twins of Water Infrastructures and aims to test one of their digital twin applications over the 5G network provided by VITAL-5G. To handle the diversity of data sources (virtual/real devices, assets and knowledge elements) diTTo Digital Twins incorporates mechanisms to manage data acquisition in real time. The aim is not only to retrieve data from devices but to also aggregate information from any other systems and data sources available.

1.3.1 diTTo IoT controller

This Network Application is designed to support data acquisition from IoT devices and sensors, persistence and serving of internal representations to the developed Digital Twin User Interfaces over the 5G network. The network performance characteristics of the 5G network regarding latency will allow the Digital Twin to represent the close to real-time state of the digitalized assets. The Network Application is also designed to support incoming messages and commands from the Digital Twin interfaces which are forwarded to actuators of the controlled assets.

1.4 Network application from the 3rd party experimenter Always Connected Consultants (ACC)

The VITAL-5G 3rd party experimenter ACC is a software architecture, development and delivery consulting start-up, created in March 2021, with the aim to be “Always and all ways connect.ed/ing.” – through agile, innovative and interdisciplinary approaches and initiatives. The founder and CEO, Eduard-Cristian POPOVICI, PhD, is the leader of SAIM (Solutions based on Agility, Innovation and Multidisciplinarity) Laboratory from UPB (POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest) – an enthusiastic promoter of entrepreneurship, team-based and project-oriented activities, personal soft skills development, advanced applied interdisciplinaries (combining information technologies like Java EE, SOA, BPM, IoT, automotive, security, health, AR/VR/XR/MR, AI/ML etc, with human sciences & technologies like marketing & branding, image & communication, future foresight, imagology, social networks etc), co-organizer of many competitions for innovation & apps development..

At the Port of Galati trial site, ACC is delivering its Flood and Fire Risk Mitigation in Wetlands Using MicroWire Sensing application. In particular, ACC have redesigned their software to a Network Application for this project to test their Flood and Fire Risk Mitigation in Wetlands Using MicroWire Sensing (FF-RIWER), which is suitable to use to process real-time data transmitted through the 5G connection in the port and the UC2 Network Application VS9. The flood and fire risk mitigation solution that will be deployed as Network Application will help to avoid dangerous events in the port and ship area as well as enrich the business intelligence tools already existing with ship specific information.

1.4.1 Flood and Fire Risk Mitigation Network Application

The Network Application that ACC is developing in the context of the VITAL-5G project is aimed at creating flood and fire risk mitigation using novel flood sensors based on MicroWire sensing technology, customized for port and ship areas. It will process real-time data using business intelligence tools to provide valuable input (such as sudden increase in water level, temperature as well as the existence of smoke), which will then be used by a visual alerting module in order to offer monitoring components that are available for a port administering authority for better crisis assessment and early response to threats.

For the purpose of developing this Network Application, ACC’s business intelligence tools are only processing data from environmental sensors, but it can benefit from data from the depth sensor as well as GPS and AIS data (provided by VS9). Therefore, the plan is to leverage supplemental data provided by the Network Applications developed in UC2 to devise a new Network Application capable of providing information to port administrating authorities as well as crew on the ship.

1.5 Network application from the 3rd party experimenter Beam Innovation SRL (BEAM)

The VITAL-5G 3rd party experimenter BEAM is a research performing SME, that is able to offer market-oriented research services in a broad area, ranging from fog and cloud computing platform development and configurations, building software applications for such platforms, in a privacy-by-design approach, going to Security, Internet-of-Things, 4G and 5G networks, optimization techniques, software development and finally in mobile application development and wireless access technologies. Its main customers are in industry, tourism, agriculture, public health, and education. It already benefits from the exploitation of research results in previous projects.

1.5.1 Blockchain-based supply chain Network Application

The Network Application that BEAM is considering in the context of the VITAL-5G project is aimed at creating an application for GHG emission traceability, customized for port and ship areas. BEAM’s software is a blockchain-type system and can collect different input data (tested for gas sensor data currently) through a back-end server

placed on top of the Hyperledger Fabric framework. The server offers REST-based APIs for interacting with the blockchain system, both for registering transactions in the blockchain and for executing smart contracts. The platform is also provided with a front-end client application that allows users to interact with the system without the need for technical knowledge. Also, as the server also provides programming APIs, any other potential interested actors (e.g. third-party developers) can connect to the system and develop new products and services that use the platform. BEAM plans to leverage the 5G network in the port of Galati, their own and existing sensors for collecting data (via VS9 and VA6) to be introduced in their system and monitor GHG emissions in port areas. The final purpose is to provide an inventory on port and ship emissions in the port of Galati and, further, in other ports around EU.